

Master's Thesis

Point- vs. diffuse-source pollution:
*uncertainty-aware attribution analysis in
Mediterranean agricultural river basins with
sparse water quality data.*

Author: Konstantin Pascal Walter

Supervisor: Cesar Rubén Fernandez De Villaran San
Juan

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As most scientific work, this thesis rests on collective effort for data, models, and discussion.

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Abstract

In Mediterranean catchments, sparse and predominantly low-flow water-quality monitoring limits reliable attribution of point and diffuse nutrient sources. This thesis developed a reproducible GIS-Python-SWAT workflow for the Cubillas catchment, southern Spain, to propagate uncertainty in two major input groups: urban wastewater point loads (WASTE) and soil nutrient initialization as diffuse loads (SOIL). Scenario specific uncertainty envelopes were evaluated against observed total nitrogen (TN) and total phosphorus (TP) concentrations and using sensitivity metrics, shifts relative to a BASE simulation, and separate diagnostics for baseflow and high-flow conditions.

Results showed contrasting nutrient pathways. TN was consistently dominated by diffuse soil inputs across flow regimes, with wastewater contributing only about 10% of the combined signal. TP was strongly regime-dependent: diffuse soil inputs dominated during storm events, producing approximately 40 times larger load shifts than the wastewater scenario. During baseflow, the diffuse TP signal weakened and wastewater became comparable to soil inputs. Without water-quality calibration, the combined W+S scenario bracketed 74% of baseflow TP observations and 77% of baseflow TN observations, although coverage did not always imply low bias. Model performance deteriorated during high-flow events, with TN coverage falling to about 40% and TP being strongly overestimated, indicating limitations in storm routing and sediment-associated phosphorus transport.

Overall, the workflow provides a transparent method for source attribution under limited data, identifies monitoring gaps, and supports targeted refinement of event-based sampling, peak-flow calibration, and Monte Carlo enabled uncertainty propagation.

Keywords

nonpoint contamination, hydrological modelling, sparse monitoring, sensitivity, monte carlo, pipeline

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Introduction

The EU Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC, 2000) is a cornerstone of European environmental law, aiming to protect and improve the quality of all water bodies. It requires member states to achieve at least “good ecological status” for rivers, lakes, groundwater, and coastal waters by 2027. In this context, understanding and predicting water quality—and how it responds to human-induced pressures and restoration measures—is critical and imperative. Yet this understanding faces multiple challenges. First, multiple variables are used to characterize water quality. For example, the US Geological Survey lists up to 24,898 variables across 17 categories (<https://help.waterdata.usgs.gov/codes-and-parameters/parameters>). Second, but not less important, the transport and fate of heat, dissolved, and suspended substances is controlled by a series of complex and interacting processes. These vary in space, time and under distinct environmental conditions. Moreover, available water-quality data are often sparse in space, inconsistent in-time, and limited. Most water-quality variables still require manual and labor-intensive measurements using ‘grab samples’ that are taken to the laboratory and analyzed. There are sensors that can be used for routine, automated measurements, but only for a few water-quality variables (mainly temperature, dissolved oxygen, specific conductance, nitrite/nitrite or dissolved organic carbon, Yaroshenko et al. 2020). The number of sites where those routine, high-frequency measurements are available, and the length of the records is very limited. Given these multiple layers of complexity, understanding water quality can be a challenging task (Zhi et al., 2023).

During the past few decades, our understanding of the physical, chemical, and microbiological processes governing biogeochemical cycles in inland waters has advanced substantially. However, our ability to predict water quality in inland water bodies in response to long- and short-term changes in the landscape, hydro-meteorological forcing, or management interventions remains limited. Consequently, significant challenges persist in managing, controlling, and improving river and reservoir water quality, and many problems continue to this day. In Spain, for example, nearly 90% of the more than 1,600 man-made reservoirs have been reported as eutrophic or at risk of eutrophication due to increased nutrient loads from urbanization, industrialization, and intensive agriculture (Rueda et al., 2024). Nutrient enrichment—primarily nitrogen and phosphorus—is evidenced by the increasing frequency of algal (including cyanobacterial) blooms, near-bottom hypoxia during summer stratification, and the subsequent mobilization of reduced substances, leading to serious consequences for drinking water, fisheries, and, and the overall integrity of freshwater ecosystems (Smith et al., 2018). Most efforts in eutrophication control have traditionally focused on reducing point-source nutrient loads sources (urban/industrial effluents) through the construction or upgrading of wastewater treatment facilities, as instructed in the European Council Directive 91/271/EEC (1991). But more recently, attention has shifted toward non-point (diffuse) sources (e.g. leaching, runoff and erosion from agricultural fields) through landscape changes and adoption of agricultural best management practices. However, the relative effectiveness of point-versus non-point source pollution controls remains uncertain. Evidence from long-term studies in the United States shows mixed and context-dependent trends in nutrient concentrations in inland waters, with variable success of non-point source mitigation measures and heterogeneous responses shaped by basin-specific characteristics, legacy nutrient stores, and implementation constraints (e.g., Tomczyk et al.(2023); Zhang et al.(2022)). Specifically, the effectiveness of point versus non-point control strategies is likely to depend on the respective contributions of these sources to total nutrient loads prior to restoration. However, disentangling these contributions is inherently difficult, and

becomes especially challenging in systems where monitoring networks are sparse and the length and resolution of the existing records limited relative to the spatial and temporal variability of hydrological and biogeochemical processes. This is the case for many river basins in southernmost Europe under semi-arid Mediterranean conditions, where sampling frequencies designed to comply with the EU Water Framework Directive are insufficient to capture the pronounced hydrological variability, characterized by extreme fluctuations across temporal scales, from synoptic (event-scale) and seasonal dynamics to strong interannual variability. In such contexts, a robust modelling-based source attribution analysis is required. Hydrological and water quality models are widely used as tools for water managers, planners, and researchers to understand and predict processes at the watershed scale (Tilahun Ashine, 2022). Their usefulness largely depends on how well they represent complex biophysical dynamics and how carefully their forcings and assumptions are handled. Yet even when leveraging sophisticated approaches, uncertainty inevitably permeates model predictions of nutrient loads due to the stochastic nature of forcing and state-variable data, as well as structural limitations inherent to the models themselves. Moreover, the representation of biogeochemical processes in landscapes requires parameterization, and parameter values are often poorly constrained or unknown. Uncertainty cannot be ignored and needs to be explicitly incorporated and quantitatively assessed in source-attribution analyses, as well as in the design, implementation, and evaluation of water quality restoration and control measures informed by modelling. The implications of model uncertainty must also be clearly communicated in project reports and forecasts (Rueda et al., 2024). Such practices can help sustain stakeholder engagement and mitigate perceptions of failure when restoration outcomes diverge from expectations. Even when data limitations and parameter uncertainty restrict predictive confidence at large scales, models can still be applied heuristically to explore system dynamics (e.g. MacLeod, (2016). These exploratory uses can yield important understanding and support decision-making. Elliott et al. (2020) for example propose a heuristic load-allocation method combining simple catchment models, load limits, and upstream–downstream relationships to infer source changes needed to meet targets.

Our goal is to quantify nutrient loads from point and non-point sources—including their relative magnitudes and temporal variability—within a river network draining a Mediterranean watershed with limited water quality data. Cubillas reservoir and its contributing watershed, in southern Spain, under Mediterranean climate (Fig. 1), is taken here as a case example. The available water quality data from government monitoring programs established to comply with the requirements of the European Water Framework Directive are very limited. Only one adequate monitoring point exists upstream the reservoir, with 26 records of total phosphorus, for example, available in the 24-year period from 1998 to 2022. There are no records from 2000 to 2008, and the median frequency of sampling is quarterly. This frequency contrasts with the natural variability of inflows, with several major storm events occurring only in fall and wintertime. Total nutrient loading estimates, hence, are highly uncertain, the relative contributions of different sources being generally consistent at the order-of-magnitude scale.

The Soil Water Assessment Tool SWAT model (Arnold, Kiniry, et al., 2012) will be used to simulate nitrogen and phosphorus fluxes in the watershed within an uncertainty framework. The results will be used to identify the dominant pollution sources (point versus non-point), quantify key uncertainties in source attribution, and evaluate how simulated nutrient concentrations and loads vary between baseflow and high-flow conditions. Given the limited availability of water quality data, model predictions are constrained and must rely on as much complementary information as possible,

including qualitative and indirect evidence. In particular, sediment transport and erosion rate estimates are used to constrain biogeochemical model behaviour and reduce predictive uncertainty.

Based on the number of inhabitants in the watershed and assuming a per-capita wastewater production rate of approximately 300 L per person per day, with typical concentrations of $9\pm 7 \text{ gPm}^{-3}$ and $50\pm 30 \text{ gNm}^{-3}$ for untreated wastewater (Metcalf, 2000), point-source nutrient loads can be estimated at roughly 40 kgPd^{-1} and 200 kgNd^{-1} . These estimates are also of the same order of magnitude as those of non-point source loads. These, in turn, can be calculated from sediment loading estimates assuming that nutrients are carried in particulate form, i.e. adsorbed to sediment particles. This is particularly the case of P (Havlin, 2004). Sediment loads have been estimated from the volume of sediment accumulated in the reservoir and assuming that (1) sediments in the reservoir have a density of ca. 1590 kg/m^3 , and (2) sediment trap efficiency can be of up to 80% (see Ortega Murcia 2021). The volume of sediments is estimated in turn from series of bathymetric surveys in the reservoir at $0.12 \text{ hm}^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$. Average sediment load estimates are at $3.7 \text{ Tn ha year}^{-1}$ (or $2\cdot 10^5 \text{ T/year}$). Assuming average concentrations of P in soil of ca. 18 mgP/100g , calculated from the available soil pits in Cubillas catchment (Mapa de Suelos de la Provincia de Granada, Proyecto LUCDEME Ministerio de Medio Ambiente 20010; Ortega Murcia 2021), one gets 120 kgP d^{-1} . This is almost three times as much the average load from point sources, but, still of the same order of magnitude. And both estimates are also of the same order of magnitude as others calculated from nutrient concentrations in the river, as reported by the River Basin Authorities (0.3 gP m^{-3} , 5.5 gNm^{-3} on average, Appendix D), and publicly available average inflow rates into the reservoir ($1.6 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$, (Confederación Hidrográfica del Guadalquivir, 2025). Estimates of total P and N loads in the river are roughly at 42 kgPd^{-1} , and 765 kgNd^{-1} . Note though that reported nutrient concentrations in rivers are estimated from samples collected only 2–3 times per year, mostly during dry periods between storm events, when river flows are below peak levels, when non-point source sediment and nutrient loads from agricultural fields are expected to be highest. In addition, flow rates in the Cubillas River at the sampling point are affected by diversions from and to neighbouring watersheds. In summary total nutrient load estimates from different sources vary considerably and are highly uncertain, the relative contributions of different sources are generally consistent at the order-of-magnitude scale.

This thesis is organized as follows. In **section 2 (methodology)** we will describe the Soil Water Assessment Tool SWAT (Arnold et al. 2021), with particular emphasis on the biogeochemical sub-models used to simulate the fate and transport of nitrogen and phosphorus, and the required input data (forcing/parameters) for Cubillas. We will describe local databases and results from previous studies used to guide model construction and to evaluate the goodness of model simulations. We will briefly describe procedures followed to evaluate forcing and model parameters, and their uncertainty (cross validation) as well as the pipeline developed for reproducibility purposes. In **section 3 (results)** we will first introduce already-calibrated results of the hydrologic routines. We will show the chosen interpolation methods and their quality. Monte-Carlo inspired min-max sampling methods will be used to evaluate the impact of input data uncertainty on model results, which will be compared against measurement data sets of water quality and **discussed in section 4 (discussion)**.

This thesis aims to contribute to ongoing efforts to understand nitrogen and phosphorus transport in Mediterranean rivers under sparse monitoring conditions and increasing anthropogenic pressure related to land-use changes and climate variability. The major methodological contribution consists of a reproducible pipeline for the water quality routines of SWAT in which uncertainty in the input data is propagated to evaluate its impact on model outputs. Comparing SWAT predictions with

sparse observed data, one could establish whether the uncertainty ranges of the chosen sources are sufficient to reconcile model predictions with measurements, or whether unexplained knowledge gaps remain.

1 Methodology

Visual Abstract: Methodology in a nutshell.

1.1 Study Site

Cubillas reservoir and its contributing catchment is located within the Upper Genil River Basin (UGRB), upstream of the Iznájar reservoir in southern Spain (see Fig. 1). The UGRB is hydrologically and environmentally distinctive for several reasons. First, it drains the highest peaks of the Sierra Nevada a protected area which contributes significant snowmelt inputs to the river system. This alpine influence shapes the seasonality of flows and interacts with Mediterranean climatic variability. Second, the basin is subject to intense anthropogenic pressure, particularly in the floodplains. The metropolitan area of Granada represents a major urban centre, accompanied by extensive agricultural activity. The river does not follow an entirely natural course; water is redistributed through human interventions and is loaded with organic matter and nutrients. Until recently, few wastewater treatment facilities were in place, meaning that untreated discharges entered the river directly. Projects aimed at consolidating and upgrading treatment facilities are currently underway; however, they are not yet operational. Third, the Granada plain contains a significant aquifer, which plays an important role in water availability for both urban and agricultural uses. Finally, the basin contains six reservoirs. Two of them, sited upstream near the highest elevations of the Sierra Nevada are oligotrophic. All other reservoirs, draining areas with intensive agriculture, exhibit strong eutrophic conditions.

Within the upper Genil water system, Cubillas watershed (Figure 1) draining into Cubillas reservoir was selected as the case study to develop and test an uncertainty aware nutrient loading methodology. The University of Granada has an ongoing research program on GHG emissions, which includes a unique infrastructure deployed at the centre Cubillas reservoir, consisting of eddy-covariance tower and submerged equipment for data interpretation. The magnitude of GHG emissions from lakes and reservoirs have been shown to be linked to their eutrophic level, the largest emission occurring from shallow eutrophic systems (DelSontro et al., 2018). Cubillas reservoir is one of these systems, with high concentrations of phosphorus and nitrogen, and anoxic conditions developing near the sediments on a seasonal basis. GHG emissions have been shown to be similar in magnitude to reported values in tropical climates. Unfortunately, no current estimates exist nor measurements of nutrient loadings into Cubillas reservoir from its contributing watershed. Its contributing watershed has extensive areas of land devoted to agriculture, mainly olive-trees. Nearly 11000 ha are irrigated, with a water consumption rate of ca. 40 hm³/year, almost as much as the volume of water that flows into the reservoir each year. Urban lands are limited, being home of nearly 15000 people. This population has remained relatively stable during the last 40 years. The impact of industrial facilities (largely linked to olive oil extraction) has changed with time. Rough estimates (based on average inflow rates and average nutrient/C loads from urban areas) suggest that point-source pollution could explain, by itself, the observed concentrations.

UGRB - Geographic context

Figure 1: Upper Genil River Basin (UGRB) and its geographical context: UGRB is feeding into the Iznajar reservoir located in southern Spain.

The 638 km² catchment area draining into the Cubillas reservoir is mountainous and largely covered by extensive agricultural fields, predominantly traditional olive plantations with sparse vegetation cover. Nearly 11000 ha are irrigated, with a water consumption rate of ca. 40 hm³/year, almost as much as the volume of water that flows into the reservoir each year.

Urban lands are limited, being home of nearly 15000 people, mostly concentrated in three villages (Iznalloz, Deifontes and Cogollos Vega, see Fig. 2). This population has remained relatively stable during the last 40 years (from ~17000 in 1980 to ~15400 nowadays). Urban wastewater has historically been discharged untreated or with minimal treatment, and only recently wastewater treatment facilities are being constructed or upgraded. Loads from industrial facilities (largely linked to olive oil extraction) have changed with time, being minimal in the last few years.

Cubillas' Population and its Wastewater (WW.) discharges

Figure 2: Population density within Cubillas in 2021. Grid of 100x100m pixels according to (Goerlich, 2025). Sum of all pixels: 15446

1.2 Watershed Model: The Soil Water Assessment Tool (SWAT)

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool SWAT (Arnold, Kiniry, et al., 2012) is a process-based “watershed-scale, continuous-time, and semi-distributed hydrological model that incorporates meteorological elements, soil characteristics, land cover/use, and management practices to predict mainly stream flow, sediments, nutrient loading, and pesticide transport” (Tilahun Ashine, 2022). The model represents a watershed (or river basin) as a set of subbasins, each one consisting of a set of hydrologic response units (HRUs) - representing unique combinations of land use, soil types, and slope – draining into a river reach. Within each HRU, processes such as surface runoff, soil water balance, nutrient cycling, sediment generation, and crop cycles are simulated. Outputs from each HRU (loading of water, sediment and other constituents out of land areas in the watershed) are aggregated to the sub-basin scale, incorporated in the river network at the upstream end of the reach

and then routed downstream (Tilahun Ashine, 2022). This hierarchical structure makes it possible to simulate how local soil–land-use dynamics scale up to catchment-wide hydrology and water quality.

Figure 3: SWAT phosphorus pools and their initialization; taken from Kalcic et al. (2018)

Nutrient pools in SWAT biogeochemical model: Several pools of Nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) are considered as state variables in the soil biogeochemical model included in SWAT (Fig. 3). Nitrogen (N) is represented through distinct organic and mineral pools to capture its dynamic transformations in soil. Organic nitrogen is subdivided into conceptual compartments that reflect differing turnover rates and stabilization levels, including fresh organic matter, active humus, and stable humus fractions. These pools are characterized by progressive degrees of decomposition and biochemical stability, thereby regulating nitrogen mineralization and immobilization processes. Mineral nitrogen is represented by ammonium (NH_4^+) and nitrate (NO_3^-), which constitute the plant-available forms and are subject to rapid transformations such as nitrification, denitrification, volatilization, plant uptake, and leaching. Phosphorus (P) dynamics are similarly conceptualized through multiple interacting pools reflecting differences in bioavailability and binding strength. The model distinguishes (1) a readily available soil solution pool, referred to as the *labile phosphorus fraction*, which directly supplies plant uptake; (2) *sorbed mineral phosphorus pools*, accounting for phosphorus associated with soil particles through adsorption and precipitation reactions, and acting as intermediate reservoirs that buffer phosphorus concentrations in the soil solution; and (3) *organic phosphorus pools*, representing phosphorus contained within soil organic matter, which becomes available through mineralization processes. The *sorbed mineral phosphorus pool is further subdivided into active and stable fractions*. Organic phosphorus is also, and similarly to organic N, subdivided into three compartments with different turnover rates and stabilization levels: *fresh organic matter, active humus, and stable humus fractions*. The fresh organic phosphorus pool represents the P contained in recent plant residues and organic inputs (e.g., crop residues, manure, litter) that have not yet been incorporated into the humic soil organic matter. Its magnitude is determined

dynamically from plant residue inputs (crop biomass remaining after harvest), organic amendments (e.g., manure, organic fertilizers), and surface litter and root residues, which are defined through management operations and crop parameters. The exchange among solution, sorbed, and organic pools governs phosphorus availability and long-term soil fertility dynamics. Together, this multi-pool representation of nitrogen and phosphorus allows the model to simulate nutrient cycling processes with sufficient mechanistic detail to reflect temporal variability in nutrient availability, plant uptake, and environmental losses. The size of the pools will vary not only because of biologically-mediated or chemical processes (e.g. mineralization, sorption and desorption, biological uptake, etc.), but also in response to transport processes that reallocate nutrients in the watershed from hillslopes to the channels, and, routed downstream through the channel network. The timing, magnitude and mechanism of transport varies depending on the nutrient considered and the form of those nutrients. Nitrate, for example, is treated as fully dissolved and is transported with surface runoff, lateral flow, and percolation. Particulate constituents are mobilized during high-rainfall events attached to sediment particles, whereas dissolved constituents travel with runoff and subsurface flows even in response to weak-to-moderate rainfall events. SWAT assumes that surface runoff interacts primarily with the thin active surface layer of the soil. The concentration of labile/solution P in this layer largely controls dissolved P export, whereas particulate P export scales with erosion and an enrichment ratio favouring finer particles. Two coefficients (specified in the *.bsn* input file) control the partitioning of mineral phosphorus between runoff and percolation: the phosphorus soil partitioning coefficient (PHOSKD) and the phosphorus percolation coefficient (PPERCO). PHOSKD relates the solution P concentration in the top 10 mm of soil to that in surface runoff, whereas PPERCO relates the solution P concentration in the top 10 mm of soil to that in the percolating water (Neitsch et al., 2011).

At the watershed scale, nutrient exports generated at the Hydrologic Response Unit (HRU) level are aggregated and introduced at the upstream end of the corresponding sub-basin reaches. These loads represent the integrated effects of soil processes, land management, and hydrological transport occurring within each HRU. Once delivered to the stream network, nutrients are routed downstream through the river system according to the model's hydrological routing scheme. During in-stream transport, nutrient concentrations are subject to further transformations governed by biogeochemical processes analogous to those simulated in the soil compartment (i.e. mineralization, nitrification, denitrification, biological uptake, exchanges between dissolved and particulate phases, and settling or resuspension of particulate forms). Any constituent (particulate or dissolved) in the river channel may either dilute or exhibit concentration spikes depending on hydrological connectivity and source contributions (Gentry et al., 2007; Jiang et al., 2021).

Nutrient & Organic M. Initialization

Figure 4: Schema of SWAT Nutrient Initialization. Red variables can be forced by the user. If not set by the user, SWAT calculates their magnitude from other variables or presets via conversion factors (represented via the edges of the above schema).

The five soil nitrogen pools representing organic (fresh organic N, stable and active humic organic N), and mineral (ammonium and nitrate) forms of nitrogen in the soil are initialized as follows by default (Fig. 4). Humic organic N (if not set directly via *SOL_ORGN* in *.chm*; mg N kg⁻¹) is derived from soil organic carbon (set in *.sol*), using a fixed C:N ratio of 14:1, and partitioned into active and stable organic N pools, with 2% assigned to the active fraction and 98% to the stable fraction. Fresh organic N is calculated as a fixed fraction (0.15%) of the initial plant residue on the soil surface (RSDIN) if specified in the *.hru* input files, otherwise set to 0. Finally, nitrate can be initialized via *SOL_NO3* in the *.chm* input file. If not provided, SWAT assigns small default values to mineral N pools (NO₃ ≈ 7 mgN kg⁻¹, and NH₄ ≈ 0.5 mgN kg⁻¹).

Fresh and humic organic P pools and the three inorganic pools (labile, active, and stable) are initialized as follows. Initial phosphorus in the fresh organic pool is derived from the amount of plant residue present on the soil surface (RSDIN) if specified in the *.hru* input files, assuming a phosphorus concentration of 0.03% in plant residues (Neitsch et al., 2011). The humic organic P pool (if not set directly via *SOL_ORGP* in *.chm*) is derived from soil organic carbon (set in *.sol*), assuming C:N and N:P ratios of 14:1 and 8:1, respectively (Neitsch et al., 2011; Vadas & White, 2010). Humic organic P is then partitioned into active and stable organic P pools, with 2% assigned to the active fraction and 98% to the stable fraction. As for the mineral fraction, it can optionally be initialized from soil tests, via *SOL_SOLP* in the *.chm* input files. If soil tests are not available, “the concentration of solution phosphorus in all layers is initially set to 5 mg/kg soil [...] representative of unmanaged land [and] 25 mg/kg soil in the plow layer is considered representative of cropland” (Neitsch et al., 2011, p. 232). The Phosphorus Availability Index (PSP or PAI) controls the partitioning of mineral phosphorus between the soil solution (*SOL_SOLP*) and the sorbed (adsorbed) phase. PSP is a dimensionless coefficient that describes how much of the soil’s mineral phosphorus is in the soil solution (available for transport and plant uptake) versus attached to soil particles. Its

value, specified in the *.sol* file, typically ranges from 0.01 to 0.7, with a default value of 0.4. If PSP is not provided in the *.sol* file, the model estimates it internally from soil properties, primarily clay content, using the relationship $PSP=0.4-0.0004\times\text{clay}(\%)$. The sorbed mineral phosphorus pool is further subdivided into active and stable fractions, assumed to be fixed at 20% and 80%, respectively. A short equilibration (or warm-up) period is recommended, regardless of the nutrient considered, to allow soil nutrient pools to stabilize before analysis (Neitsch, 2012; Tetra Tech, 2015).

In summary, SWAT considers for P & N and initialization any changes made to these variables:

- SOL_SOLP(.chm): initial solution/labile P, mg kg^{-1} .
- SOL_ORGP(.chm): initial humic organic P, mg kg^{-1} .
- SOL_NO3(.chm): initial nitrate-N, mg kg^{-1} .
- SOL_ORGN(.chm): initial humic organic N, mg kg^{-1} .
- RSDIN (.hru) Initial residue cover [kg/ha], translates to fresh organic N & P

A detailed simulation of nutrient dynamics within the soil profile of agricultural fields will require comprehensive and high-resolution input data describing both agricultural management practices and inherent soil properties (see for example, Huertas-Fernández et al 2025). Agricultural practices directly regulate nutrient inputs (fertilization), transformations, redistribution, plant uptake, and losses through leaching, volatilization, or runoff. Detailed information on fertilization practices, including fertilizer type (mineral or organic), nutrient composition, application rates, timing, frequency, and method of application, is needed. Irrigation management must also be characterized in terms of method, application volume, scheduling, and water quality, as these practices influence nutrient mobility and availability. Tillage operations, including type, depth, frequency, and timing, affect soil structure, aeration, and organic matter decomposition, thereby influencing nutrient cycling processes. Furthermore, crop rotation schemes, planting and harvest dates, rooting depth, biomass production, and residue management practices must be incorporated to adequately simulate plant nutrient uptake and organic matter inputs. In addition to management data, accurate characterization of soil physical, chemical, and biological properties is required. Soil texture, bulk density, porosity, and hydraulic conductivity govern water movement and nutrient transport within the soil profile. Chemical parameters such as initial nutrient concentrations, soil organic matter content, cation exchange capacity, pH, and carbon-to-nitrogen ratio influence nutrient retention and transformation processes. Biological activity, including mineralization, nitrification, and denitrification rates, further determines nutrient availability and losses. Finally, climatic variables such as precipitation, temperature, evapotranspiration, and solar radiation serve as key external drivers of soil water balance and biogeochemical processes. The integration of detailed management information, soil characteristics, and climatic data ensures robust and reliable simulation of nutrient dynamics in agricultural systems. SWAT incorporates a comprehensive internal database containing crop parameters and generic management practices (planting, tillage, fertilization, and irrigation schedules) for a wide range of crops and land uses. These

predefined datasets, stored in management databases (e.g., CROP.DAT, FERT.DAT, TILL.DAT, URBAN.DAT) and operation files (.MGT), enable simulation of crop growth, soil processes, and nutrient dynamics, even in the absence of site-specific management information, and allow alternative management scenarios to be explored across diverse agricultural systems.

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) has become one of the most widely applied models for watershed-scale hydrology and water quality assessment. Extensive documentation and a large user community underpin method transparency and reproducibility. Its popularity stems from its ability to integrate multiple environmental drivers within a continuous, process-based modelling framework. Specifically, SWAT couples climate variability, land use, soil characteristics, topography, and agricultural management practices to simulate the movement of water, sediments, and nutrients across complex catchment systems. Its flexibility, extensive documentation, and large international user community have further contributed to its widespread adoption in both research and applied water resource management contexts (see, for example, Janjić and Tadić, 2013, Tan et al, 2020, Francesconi et al. 2016, Yen et al. 2020, Zang et al. 2023, or the official SWAT webpage).

1.3 SWAT-Cubillas Model Setup: Hydrology and Soil Erosion

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (Arnold et al., 2012) was used to simulate water, sediment, and nutrient fluxes into Cubillas reservoir from its contributing watershed over a 40-year period starting in January 1981. This time window broadly complies with methodological recommendations in the literature, which suggest using climate records of at least 15–30 years to obtain robust results in distributed hydrological models (Arnold, Kiniry, et al., 2012; D. N. Moriasi et al., 2007). Moreover, it encompasses both prolonged drought episodes and significant wet periods, thereby representing the hydroclimatic variability characteristic of the southern Iberian Peninsula (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2014).

Cubillas Subbasins & Land Uses

Figure 5: SWAT Cubillas subbasins, corresponding reaches and soil types.

The basin was subdivided into 17 sub-basins (see Fig. 5), with the main outlet located at the exact position of the Cubillas Reservoir dam. Additionally, secondary outlet points were defined (1) near the headwaters and (2) upstream of junctions within the network of river reaches defined by the Guadalquivir River Basin Authority (Confederación Hidrográfica del Guadalquivir (CHG), 2023). Each reach in this network is designated as a water body for monitoring and water quality control. This approach ensures that each reach or water body within the river network is associated with a corresponding sub-basin in the model. A National scale Digital Terrain Model DTM with a spatial resolution of 25×25 m (Instituto Geográfico Nacional, 2020) was used to delineate the drainage network and to subdivide the catchment into subbasins (Winchell et al., 2013). In addition, the DTM was used to derive five slope classes for the catchment (Neitsch et al., 2011; Winchell et al., 2013). The model was forced using daily precipitation, as well as minimum and maximum temperatures, estimated from a network of meteorological stations maintained by various national and regional agencies. Rainfall and temperature records were interpolated to the centroids of the 17 sub-basins identified within the catchment following the approach of Herrero et al. (2009) (see also Aguilar et al., 2010; Polo et al., 2010).

The soil database was developed by integrating two different sources of information and applying the pedotransfer functions proposed by Saxton and Rawls (2006) to estimate soil parameters not directly available in the original databases (Bouma, 1989). In particular, the following raster datasets were used: (1) the European Soil Database (ESDB) and derived continental-scale products for soil depth and texture, porosity organic carbon, and bulk density (Panagos et al., 2012, 2022), accessed through the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC); and (2) the National Soil Erosion Inventory (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico, 2020) for the USLE K factor (soil erodibility). The Lithological Map of Andalusia (Junta de Andalucía, 2005) was used to identify soil class units and their spatial extent, the properties of each class were derived from the raster maps by averaging the values of all pixels within each class. A total of 8 soil-type classes were identified in the watershed (Fig. 5, Appendix C).

Land use was characterized using a national dataset (Sistema de Información sobre Ocupación del Suelo en España SIOSE), developed by the Instituto Geográfico Nacional (IGN) at a reference scale of 1:25,000 (Instituto Geográfico Nacional, 2015). The national land-use classification was mapped to SWAT land-use classes using the lookup table shown in Appendix B. A total of 24 land use classes were identified in the watershed, with agricultural olive orchards (~40%), herbaceous crop lands (20%) and range/shrublands (16%) representing the dominant land uses (~75% of the watershed). Hydrologic Curve Number (USDA-NRCS, 2004), vegetation cover percentage, soil Manning's roughness coefficient, and the Universal Soil Loss Equation USLE cover, and management factor (C factor) were assigned to each class as defined in the SWAT database (Arnold et al., 1998).

Hydrologic Response Units HRUs were generated by intersecting soil type, land use, and slope classes. Within each HRU the hydrologic behaviour (infiltration, evapotranspiration, runoff, or erosion rates, soil moisture and nutrient content) is considered homogenous, having the same land-use, soil type and slope (Flügel, 1995; Neitsch et al., 2011). HRUs representing less than 10% of the area of a given subbasin were reclassified and incorporated into the largest HRU within that subbasin. A total of 2040 HRUs were defined, in this manner, in the watershed. With this level of discretization can landscape heterogeneity and the variability of hydrological processes the representation can be represented in an aggregated yet spatially explicit manner, optimizing, in this manner, the balance between physical realism and computational efficiency (Mamillapalli et al., 1996).

For model calibration, we used naturalized daily streamflows reconstructed from (1) inflow rates into Cubillas Reservoir, (2) diversion flows out of the watershed upstream of Cubillas at Deifontes Spring, (3) diversion flows into the river upstream of Cubillas Reservoir from Colomera Reservoir (the Colomera–Cubillas diversion), and (4) flows through a bypass tunnel that diverts peak streamflows before they enter the reservoir and discharges them back to the river downstream of the reservoir. Inflow rates into Cubillas Reservoir were estimated from daily outflow rates, storage volumes, and evaporation rates, following standardized data acquisition and quality control protocols. All data were provided by the Guadalquivir River Basin Authority and were subjected to a review process prior to use to ensure the consistency and reliability of the data employed in the model calibration. Average erosion rates and sediment load estimates were constructed from the topography of the inundated basin and a series of lake bottom bathymetries conducted in 2001, 2017 and 2019, and made available to us by the Guadalquivir River Basin Authority. Mass sediment loads were estimated from the volume of sediments accumulated in the lake basin from its construction to 2019, assuming a trap efficiency of 0.82 (the average of the efficiency calculated from lake morphometry using three approaches (including Brown, 1943; Heinemarm, 1981; Ortega, 2021; USDA-SCS, 1983) and a density for accumulated sediments of 1590 kgm^{-3} , as measured experimentally (Ortega, 2021)

The calibration process focused on those parameters with the greatest influence on key hydrological processes, including surface runoff generation, infiltration, and baseflow dynamics (see Appendix A). The selection of these parameters was based on prior sensitivity analyses and documented experience in the literature for catchments with Mediterranean characteristics (Abbaspour et al., 2015; D. N. Moriasi et al., 2007; Zabaleta et al., 2014). Appendix A's table summarizes, for each parameter, the adjustment method applied (replacement - V - or relative - R - adjustment, Neitsch et al., 2011) and the range of values explored during the optimization process. The calibration was conducted using the Sequential Uncertainty Fitting, version 2 (SUFI-2), a widely used algorithm for calibrating hydrological and environmental models that accounts for model

uncertainty. SUFI-2, developed by Abbaspour et al. (2007) and implemented in the SWAT-CUP tool for the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) involved over 9,000 iterative simulations that systematically explored the multidimensional parameter space and minimized the uncertainty associated with model predictions (Abbaspour et al., 2007). The Coefficient of Determination (R^2), Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE), Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE), and Percent Bias (PBIAS) were used to quantify the degree of agreement between simulated and observed values during the calibration and validation phases (see D. N. Moriasi et al., 2007; Moriasi et al., 2015). To select the optimal simulation from the set of results generated by SUFI-2, a multi-factor ranking procedure was established based on the four selected efficiency statistics. First, all simulations were sorted in descending order according to their Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) value, considered the primary goodness-of-fit indicator due to its capacity to evaluate the agreement between simulated and observed streamflows in both magnitude and timing (Nash & Sutcliffe, 1970). This ranking was then refined by successively applying secondary criteria: priority was given to those simulations with better Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE) values, which integrally balances correlation, variability bias, and mean bias (Gupta et al., 2009); subsequently, the coefficient of determination (R^2), which measures the proportion of variance explained by the model, was considered; and finally, Percent Bias (PBIAS) was applied to penalize those simulations with excessive systematic biases in the estimation of total volumes. The final simulation, designated configuration '219', was the one that occupied the highest position in this multi-factor ranking. The magnitude of the calibrated parameters for the simulation occupying the highest position in our multi-factor ranking and serving as a reference for the present study is also presented and shown also in the Appendix A table. The USLE cover and management (C) factors assigned to the land-use classes in the watershed were reduced from the values assumed in the SWAT database, so that simulated sediment yields were comparable to long-term erosion rates estimated from reservoir bathymetric surveys. Furthermore, the spatial discretization of the watershed was revisited by modifying the thresholds used to define HRUs, resulting in a more precise delineation of sediment source areas.

1.3.1 SWAT-Cubillas Model Setup: Nutrients and Organic Matter

In this thesis, point sources are explicitly estimated from population distributions while soil nutrient pools are initialized interpolating local soil data. Point sources of nutrients will be assumed to originate primarily from untreated urban wastewater discharges, and their loads were estimated using local population statistics together with literature values for per capita water use and nutrient concentrations in wastewater. Local soil databases were used to estimate the initial magnitude of soil nutrient pools at the HRU scale. The uncertainty associated with the local estimates of initial soil nutrient pools and point-source nutrient loads was propagated, and its effect on model uncertainty was evaluated explicitly. Sparse publicly available data were compiled, harmonized, interpolated, and aggregated at the HRU level, and converted into formats compatible with SWAT input files. Other factors influencing non-point source pollution levels, such as crop parameters, growth cycles, and management practices (e.g., irrigation and fertilization), are considered as well-known (i.e. deterministic inputs) and taken from the model's default internal database.

Figure 6: schematic inputs to SWAT nutrient model and how to validate outputs; turquoise elements are subject to this study

1.3.2 Point Source: Continuous Urban Wastewater Discharge

Municipal wastewater is considered the dominant point-source of nutrients and organic carbon in Cubillas. Currently, wastewater is discharged untreated to the rivers. New treatment facilities are under construction (Deifontes and Iznalloz) but still not operational. Hence, for this study, all municipal discharges are assumed to be untreated. Other potential sources, including industrial effluents, tourism-related discharges, and residues from livestock are assumed negligible. Historically, olive mills discharged olive oil wastewater (“alpechín”) directly into rivers, which likely caused high seasonal loads of organic matter and nutrients. However, no consistent datasets on industrial discharges have been encountered for the study area.

The continuous population density maps published by (Goerlich, 2025) were used to estimate the spatial distribution and interannual variability of population at the sub-basin scale. The dataset consists of decadal maps of population distribution from 1971 to 2021, with information provided at 100 m² grid-cell resolution. Only one point source can be specified per reach/sub-basin in SWAT, hence, multiple discharges within the same subbasins were aggregated. For that purpose, the population raster information contained in (Goerlich, 2025) was clipped to the basin extent and pixel counts were aggregated to obtain the number of inhabitants at the sub-basin level. Decadal values (1971–2021) were linearly interpolated to form annual series.

Per-capita water use was allowed to vary between 100 and 400 L person⁻¹day⁻¹ to account for uncertainty and variability among sites and information sources. Jones et al. (2021), for example, suggest an average value of approximately 240 L person⁻¹ day⁻¹. Similar values (280 L person⁻¹ day⁻¹) are reported by Jódar-Abellán et al. (2019). On the lower end, the Spanish National Statistical Institute reports daily consumption for some communities as low as 100 L person⁻¹ day⁻¹ (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2022). However, a report on water resources in the Genil River Basin indicates that per-capita water use in some villages within the Cubillas catchment can reach up to 400 L person⁻¹ day⁻¹ (Murillo Díaz & Navarro lañez, 2006).

No local information on nutrient and organic matter concentrations in wastewater was available for any urban site in the Cubillas basin. Typical ranges of nutrient (phosphorus and nitrogen) and organic matter concentrations (carbonaceous biochemical oxygen demand, CBOD₅) in untreated wastewater were therefore taken from Metcalf (2000), see Table 1. BOD₅ concentrations reported were assumed to be equivalent to CBOD₅ (as required by SWAT), given reported BOD₅/CBOD₅ ratios of 1.05–1.30 (Muirhead et al., 2006). Dissolved oxygen and chlorophyll-a concentrations in wastewater were assumed to be negligible.

Table 1 — Point-source uncertainty bounds of wastewater composition (mg L⁻¹); taken from Metcalf (2000)

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>
<i>Organic Nitrogen (ORGNYR)</i>	8	35
<i>Organic Phosphorus (ORGPYR)</i>	1	5
<i>Nitrate (NO₃YR)</i>	0	0
<i>Ammonium (NH₃YR)</i>	12	50
<i>Nitrite (NO₂YR)</i>	0	0
<i>Mineral Phosphorus (MINPYR)</i>	3	10
<i>Suspended Sediment (SEDYR)</i>	350	1200
<i>CBOD₅ (CBODYR)</i>	110	400
<i>Dissolved Oxygen (DISOXYR)</i>	0	2
<i>Chlorophyll-a (CHLAYR)</i>	0.000	0.002

1.3.3 Diffuse Source: Initialization of Soil Nutrient Pools

Three local datasets were evaluated as potential sources of information to initialize soil nutrient and organic carbon *Corg* pools in SWAT. Overall, the sampling density of the available soil surveys is helpful for regional-scale characterization; however, it may be insufficient to resolve spatial variability at the finer scale of the study area. To mitigate limitations associated with sparse sampling, the analysis incorporated all data from the Upper Genil River Basins UGRB (contributing watershed to Iznajar Reservoir) together with a 30 km surrounding buffer. This approach minimizes boundary artifacts and reduces edge effects within the study area (contributing watershed to Cubillas reservoir) in the interpolation procedure. The three data sets are:

A. CARBOSOL (Llorente et al., 2018). This data set includes 82 data points in UGRB. It offers a regional compilation of soil carbon C, nitrogen N (ppm), C/N ratio and other related properties with standardized metadata (see associated readme, data model). However, phosphorus (P) content is not reported in the dataset.

B. LUCAS 2018 (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2022) LUCAS Topsoil 2018 is an EU-wide survey with harmonized protocols and a coarse sampling grid; the dataset includes SOC, total N, and Olsen-P among other variables. A total of 79 data points is within UGRB, and only 10 within Cubillas. The dataset is useful for regional-scale assessments and to verify plausible parameter ranges. However, due to limited sampling density it may not be adequate to characterize spatial variability at the scale of HRUs.

C. REDIAM – Geochemical soil profiles of Andalucía (Consejería de Agricultura, Ganadería, Pesca y Desarrollo Sostenible, 2019). The dataset includes information from 334 sampling locations in the Upper Genil River Basin (UGRB; upstream of the Iznájar Reservoir), where soil pits were excavated for analysis. Of these, 18 sites are located within the study area (upstream of the Cubillas Reservoir). The dataset comprises soil profile analyses compiled from multiple studies conducted across Andalucía at different times. In particular, it includes data from project (Proyecto de Lucha contra la Desertificación en el Mediterráneo, Ministerio de Medio Ambiente 2010), an extensive regional soil survey and characterization program conducted in 1990s in southern Spain, that provided standardized soil profile descriptions and laboratory analyses. All observations included in the data set were used to evaluate the spatial variability of soil chemical properties, regardless of sampling time, assuming that soil nitrogen, phosphorus, and organic carbon contents remain temporally invariant. The dataset provides high spatial sampling density and harmonized laboratory measurements with standardized reporting units for key soil chemical parameters, including soil organic carbon (SOC, %), total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TN, %), C/N ratio, and plant-available phosphorus determined using the Olsen extraction method (Olsen-P, mg P₂O₅ /100g or ppm P₂O₅ depending on the original data source). Analytical results are reported by soil horizons of varying thickness and are accompanied by supporting documentation and data models. Only the analytical results of topsoil horizons were considered for model initialization. Table 2 summarizes the conversions and their bounds involved in preparing soil pool initialization data from REDIAM soil pit records.

The available TKN and Olsen-P data from these REDIAM soil pits, filtered to topsoil horizons and cross-checked for coordinate and unit consistency, were interpolated to yield continuous rasters with a 50 x 50 m resolution. Initialization only targeted the active topsoil layer used in the SWAT setup (mean thickness=282cm, SD=24cm). Values from the REDIAM soil horizons closest to the surface were retained, regardless of the reported horizon thickness. To reduce edge effects associated with sparse sampling, the interpolation exercise used all points within the perimeter of the Upper Genil River Basin, together with an additional 30 km buffer zone. The resulting rasters were subsequently clipped to the Cubillas catchment. Eight interpolation methods available in ArcGIS Pro were assessed, including four kriging variants, kernel interpolation, inverse distance weighting (IDW), radial basis functions, and polynomial interpolation. The performance of the alternative interpolation methods was evaluated using leave-one-out cross-validation, and the resulting metrics were ranked using a weighted scoring scheme that prioritized minimizing bias (weight = 3), followed by minimizing root mean square error (RMSE; weight = 2) and maximum absolute error (weight = 1). This evaluation was conducted separately for the phosphorus (P) and nitrogen (N) datasets to identify the most suitable interpolation method for each variable.

Pixel values of TKN (%) and Olsen-P (reported as mg P₂O₅ per 100 g of soil) were averaged within each HRU and the resulting means were converted to mg kg⁻¹. To account for the high measurement and interpolation uncertainty in a pipeline-compatible way the P75 of the absolute relative error (200% for Olsen-P, 99% for TKN) from the overall interpolation leave-one-out validation were used to

perturb the HRU averages of the original interpolation to acquire conservative min–max bounds. The lower bound was capped at zero if perturbations of HRU averages are negative. The N and P pools in SWAT were initialized from these HRU min–max bounds of TKN and Olsen-P interpolations as follows. TKN was assumed to be predominantly in the form of organic N (Rapisarda et al., 2022), ammonium concentration being negligible (as stated in Arnold et al. 2012, see also Tipping et al. (2016). Organic N, in turn, was assumed to be 97% of total N (TN), the remaining fraction of TN being nitrate. Olsen-P was used as a proxy for labile or solution phosphorus, following approaches suggested in the literature (Chaubey & Migliaccio, 2006; Wang et al., 2020). However, Olsen-P can underestimate the isotopically exchangeable phosphorus fraction (Braun et al., 2019). Therefore, Olsen-P values were multiplied by a factor (uncertain) ranging from 1 to 5 to initialize the labile P pool. As for the initial values of the Organic P pool, this was estimated from the organic N pool assuming a N:P ratio (uncertain) varying between 14:1 and 5:1, as reported in McGill & Cole (McGill & Cole, 1981) rather than SWAT's default 8:1 ratio. Fresh organic N and P pools were left at SWAT default initialization; locally derived HRU-scale estimates were used only to initialize organic N, nitrate, labile P, and organic P of the uppermost soil layer.

Table 2 — Diffuse-source conversions and uncertainty bounds

Source / input	Conversion / operation	SWAT / intermediate variable (output)	Range (lower–upper factor)
Interpolated Total Kjeldahl N raster (% TKN; HRU average)	<i>multiply</i> × 10 000 (% → mg kg ⁻¹)	Total Kjeldahl N (<i>TKN</i> ; mg kg ⁻¹)	p75 absolute relative error; factor → <i>lower</i> : 0.01, <i>upper</i> : 1.99
Interpolated Olsen-P raster (mg/100 g P ₂ O ₅ ; HRU Average)	<i>multiply</i> × 10 (→ mg kg ⁻¹) × 0.4364 (P ₂ O ₅ →P)	Olsen-P (mg kg ⁻¹ as P)	p75 absolute relative error; factor → <i>lower</i> : 0 <i>upper</i> : 3
Total Kjeldahl N (mg kg ⁻¹)	<i>multiply</i>	Total N (TN) , mg kg ⁻¹)	<i>lower</i> : 1.03 <i>upper</i> : 1.03
<i>in its upper and lower bounds from first step</i>	<i>multiply</i>	Soil organic P	<i>lower</i> : 0.07 <i>upper</i> : 0.2
Total N (<i>TN</i> ; mg kg ⁻¹)	<i>multiply</i>	Soil organic N	<i>lower</i> : 0.97 <i>upper</i> : 0.97
		Soil NO₃⁻	<i>lower</i> : 0.03 <i>upper</i> : 0.03
Olsen-P (mg kg ⁻¹ as P)	<i>multiply</i> (O.-P to labile pool)	Soil labile P	<i>lower</i> : 1 <i>upper</i> : 5

1.3.4 Validation: River Water Quality Data

River water quality in the Upper Genil River Basin (UGRB) is routinely monitored by the Water Authorities (Confederación Hidrográfica del Guadalquivir) to ensure compliance with the requirements of the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD). Data from the official monitoring program were provided by the central office for Water Quality Control (“Comisaría de Aguas”) of CHG and were used for comparison with the model predictions. Comparable WFD datasets for Spanish basins are publicly accessible through the national open-data catalogue at <https://datos.gob.es/>. The WFD monitoring programmes combine surveillance, operational, and investigative components. Their design specifies the monitoring stations, quality elements, indices, and frequencies, and is revised on a six-year cycle. The sampling frequencies at which the data are available are suitable for ecological status assessments; however, they are insufficient for direct load estimation.

The observational dataset includes, among others, concentration records for Total Phosphorus (mg P/l), Phosphate (mg PO₄/l), Total Nitrogen (mg N/l), Kjeldahl Nitrogen (mg N/l), Nitrate (mg NO₃/l), Nitrite (mg NO₂/l), Ammonium (mg NH₄/l), and 5-day Biochemical Oxygen Demand (mg O₂/l) as an organic-load indicator (CBOD/BOD proxy).

Cubillas subbasins and respective WFD measurement locations

Figure 7: MDA monitoring locations within Cubillas. Close stations were grouped under their higher order station number. The 30304 group (30304 & 30304_2) was identified as best for model validation.

The monitoring network (see Fig. 7) includes three sampling points within Cubillas reservoir (30303-O, 30303-C, 30303B). These were not used for validation, given that nutrient dynamics in

lakes and reservoirs, under stratified conditions, are not simulated correctly in SWAT. Only the records from sites 30304 and 30304_2, both in subbasin 13 (see Fig. 7, green colored) and close to each other (approx. 500 m apart), were used for validation purposes. Both sites are located downstream of major diversion infrastructures, as such these stations may not perfectly reflect concentrations under undisturbed conditions, as simulated in SWAT. Records from other sites were discarded for several reasons. Sites 30300, 30299, and 30298, for example, do not have valid observations within the 1981–2020 study period. Station 30309 has only very recent data. As for sampling site 30101, it had a relatively high temporal width and resolution (much of the reported data is below detection limit though), but it was discarded for having little influence from point sources but might warrant future consideration (See Table 3).

Total Nitrogen (TN) records were available only from March 2020 onward at all stations and therefore fall outside the modelling period. Measured total phosphorus (TP) concentrations and measured Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) plus nitrate (NO₃) concentrations, used here as an estimate of total nitrogen (TN), were compared with simulated TP and TN concentrations at reach 13. Simulated concentrations were derived from daily loads reported in the *.rch* output files (kg day⁻¹) divided by simulated daily flow (m³ day⁻¹), yielding concentrations in mg L⁻¹. As shown in Table 3, within the study period, 33 TKN samples were available between 1994 and 2018; 12 negative values were removed, reducing the usable TKN record to 1994-2001 and resulting in a median sampling interval of ≈3 months. For nitrate, 40 measurements were available between 1994 and 2019, with a median sampling interval of ≈3.5 months. For TP, 26 concentration records were available at a median interval of ≈4 months, and one negative value was removed.

For each variable, the detection limit (MDL) was approximated as the lowest reported concentration in the whole DMA dataset, and below-detection-limit entries (“LC”) were replaced with half that value. Accordingly, 11 TKN entries were set to 0.1 mg L⁻¹, one nitrate entry to 0.05 mg L⁻¹, and one TP entry to 0.005 mg L⁻¹. See Appendix D for the raw data used.

Table 3. Valid observed nutrient samples in Cubillas at monitoring stations within modeling period. N valid = non-negative numeric records + “LC” (below detection limit) records. Negative values are excluded from stats. LC records are substituted with half the lowest reported value of the respective variable in the whole dataset.

Variable	Station	N valid	N neg.	N LC	First valid sample	Span (yrs)	Median interval (days)	Mean	Median	Max
Total Phosphorus (mg P/l)	30101	71	16	40	1997-07-15	11.7	42	0.0363	0.005	0.27
	30304	25	1	1	1998-09-09	19.8	118	0.3030	0.170	1.32
	30309	11	0	0	2015-02-12	3.3	124	0.3927	0.390	0.70
Kjeldahl Nitrogen (mg N/l)	30101	44	9	35	1994-09-01	12.9	90	0.4864	0.100	3.90
	30304	21	12	11	1994-12-01	6.3	92	0.7857	0.100	3.20
	30309	4	7	0	2016-06-14	1.7	246	1.7000	1.600	1.90

Nitrate (mg No ₃ /l)	30101	162	7	19	1994-09-01	24.1	29	1.2806	1.000	7.90
	30304	40	0	1	1994-12-01	24.8	105	21.0257	15.200	77.90
	30309	13	0	0	2015-02-12	4.6	124	14.2846	12.000	42.00

1.3.5 Uncertainty Propagation and Assessment

For each variable identified as a source of uncertainty in the model, lower and upper bounds were defined based on available data and relevant literature. The Python notebook

[01_run_swat_monte_carlo.ipynb](#), developed in the context of this thesis, implements a Monte Carlo framework for randomly sampling parameter sets within predefined bounds and generating the corresponding SWAT input files for each realization of the parameter space (ensemble of inputs). Simulations are then conducted for each ensemble member to assess the impact of input-parameter uncertainty on simulated hydrological and water-quality outputs. The pipeline developed in this thesis supports fully automated Monte Carlo ensembles (random or stratified sampling) with parallel execution and run-time logging of seeds, configurations, and input snapshots. In practice, ensemble size is limited only by available computational resources. This design helps link the effects of input-data uncertainty on model outputs and follows the rationale that transparent uncertainty analysis is essential for credible nutrient modelling (Wang et al., 2020).

Instead of exploring the full uncertainty space probabilistically (full Monte Carlo approach), this thesis evaluates two deterministic scenarios based on the lower and upper bounds of the uncertain input parameters and uses the resulting range as an uncertainty envelope (min–max envelope). The simulations conducted with minimum and maximum parameter values are assumed to represent the lower and upper bounds of the model outputs, respectively. The mean of the lower and upper output bounds is used as a central estimate. This choice prioritizes interpretability having sparse observations: it avoids assumptions about input distributions and inter-parameter correlations, yields defensible bounds quickly, and decouples input uncertainty from structural/model uncertainty.

A dimensionless index (relative width) is calculated on a daily basis to quantify the relative difference between model outputs obtained using maximum and minimum parameter values. For each day t , the relative width R_t is defined as:

$$R_t = \frac{(x_{\max,t} - x_{\min,t})}{(x_{\max,t} + x_{\min,t})/2}$$

where $x_{\max,t}$ and $x_{\min,t}$ are the model outputs obtained using the upper and lower bounds of the parameter ranges, respectively. Note that, since only two simulations are considered (upper and lower parameter bounds), the arithmetic mean and median are identical by definition; thus, $(x_{\max,t} + x_{\min,t})/2$, serves as both measures of central tendency. This metric (R_t) describes the magnitude of the modeled uncertainty of variable x that results from the uncertainty in input parameter values.

1.3.6 Sensitivity to Pollution Sources

The relative influence of point-source and diffuse soil nutrient inputs on simulated nutrient concentrations upstream of the Cubillas Reservoir were quantified using a structured perturbation analysis. In this framework, one type of point-source inputs (urban discharges) and one type of diffuse/nonpoint source (soil nutrient pools) inputs were systematically varied between their minimum and maximum values (input bounds). As summarized in table 4, three minimum-maximum scenarios were considered, together with a base case scenario (BASE) corresponding to our default, water flow and sediment calibrated, SWAT configuration (no point-sources, nutrient pools in soil initialized from user assigned organic carbon OC content specified in the .sol input files, and labile P set to 5 mgP/kg). In the first scenario, .dat point-source inputs were varied between their minimum and maximum bounds while diffuse inputs were not changed from the SWAT defaults. This will be referred to as the WASTE (for wastewater) scenario. In the second one (referred to as SOIL – for soil-initialization - scenario), diffuse inputs were varied while no point sources were introduced. Finally, in the third scenario (W+S), both point- and diffuse-source inputs were simultaneously varied across their respective ranges. For each scenario, simulations using minimum and maximum input parameter values produced prediction envelopes representing the range of model outputs under input uncertainty (min–max envelopes). The relative importance of point and diffuse sources, as well as their combined effects, on model response (measured in terms of loads or concentrations) was assessed by comparing the width and divergence of those envelopes for total phosphorus (TP) and total nitrogen (TN) among scenarios. Differences in envelope width (or spread) among scenarios were used to infer source dominance and potential interactions between point and diffuse inputs. In simple terms, the comparison between the three scenarios tells us where most of the influence on P or N concentration in the model is coming from, i.e.

Table 4: Scenarios and the respective SWAT inputs used.

<i>Scenario</i>	<i>Point-source inputs</i>	<i>Soil initialization inputs</i>
BASE	No	Default SWAT
WASTE	Variable	Default SWAT
SOIL	No	Variable
W+S	Variable	Variable

WASTE (W) scenario (point sources only): If the range of river nutrient concentrations at the control point (the envelope) were wide in this scenario, it would be an indication that point sources (wastewater discharges) strongly control P/N concentrations.

SOIL (S) scenario (diffuse sources only): If the range is wide in this case, it means that runoff from land (e.g., agriculture, soil erosion) is a significant driver of nutrients concentrations in the river and loads into the reservoir.

W+S scenario (point and diffuse together): Comparing the results of this scenario to the other two, will allow us to identify the combined effect. If it is much wider than both, both sources are important and may reinforce each other. If it is similar to just one scenario, that source is dominant.

If it is only slightly larger than the sum of both sources, the sources act independently which suggests that there is no strong interaction.

In summary, by comparing the width of nutrient predictions in each scenario, one can tell whether those nutrients in the system are mainly controlled by point sources, diffuse sources, or a combination of both—and whether their effects interact or not.

1.3.7 Statistical Inference

For statistical inference—particularly for estimating uncertainty measures such as standard errors, confidence intervals, and tests of differences between scenarios—the effective sample size was used to account for strong temporal autocorrelation in the model output time series. The effective sample size n_{eff} is calculated as a function of the lag-1 autocorrelation $\hat{\rho}_1$ of the time series of the variable analyzed, which quantifies how much first order serial dependence reduces the “independent information” in the series. Here we follow Zwiers and von Storch (1995) and Yue and Wang (2004) and calculate the effective sample size as $n_{\text{eff}} = n(1 - \hat{\rho}_1)/(1 + \hat{\rho}_1)$, n being the available daily values. This approach is consistent with common treatments of persistent hydrological and water-quality time series (Li et al., 2016; McInerney et al., 2017; Hernandez-Suarez and Nejadhashemi, 2022; Decremet et al., 2014). For scenario specific statistics, n_{eff} was computed from the corresponding daily metric series; for pairwise scenario contrasts, it was computed from the daily paired-difference series.

The 95% confidence interval for the mean (CI₉₅) was calculated as follows

$$CI_{95} = \bar{x} \pm 1.96 \times SE = \bar{x} \pm 1.96 \frac{s}{\sqrt{n_{\text{eff}}}}$$

where the \bar{x} is the sample mean, and SE the standard error of the mean. This, in turn, is calculated in terms of the effective sample size n_{eff} and the sample standard deviation s (i.e. $SE = s/n_{\text{eff}}^{1/2}$). The magnitude of the 95% confidence interval around the mean (i.e. $\pm 1.96 SE$) is plotted as whiskers in the bar charts. Whiskers $CI_{95} = \pm 1.96 SD/\sqrt{n_{\text{eff}}}$ provide a visual guide to check whether apparent differences are likely to be robust. Following the “inference by eye” framework, clear non-overlap of 95% confidence intervals suggests strong evidence of meaningful separation (Cumming and Finch, 2005; Cumming and Fidler, 2009).

In the text, when comparing two simulated scenarios A and B , the term Δ is used to represent the average difference between mean values of a given variable x , expressed in the original units of the metric (% , mg L^{-1} , or kg day^{-1}). Because the scenarios are simulated over the same dates, comparisons between scenarios were treated as paired daily contrasts. Daily paired differences were first calculated as

$d_t = x_{A,t} - x_{B,t}$ where $x_{A,t}$ and $x_{B,t}$ are the values of scenarios A and B on the same simulation day t . The reported absolute difference is therefore $\Delta = \bar{d}$ where \bar{d} is the mean of the daily paired differences.

The 95% confidence interval $CI_{95}(\Delta)$ of the paired difference was constructed from the standard error of the paired-difference series, scaled to the effective sample size of that series:

$$CI_{95}(\Delta) = \bar{d} \pm 1.96 \frac{s_d}{\sqrt{n_{\text{eff},d}}}$$

where s_d is the standard deviation of the daily paired differences and $n_{eff,d}$ is the effective sample size estimated from the lag-1 autocorrelation of d_t . The paired p-value reported in the tables was obtained from the corresponding one-sample paired t-test of $H_0: \bar{d} = 0$, using the autocorrelation-adjusted standard error. Thus, the p-value tests whether the mean same-day difference between two scenarios differs from zero after accounting for temporal autocorrelation.

The relative paired difference Δ_{rel} expresses the same contrast in percentage terms. For comparisons against BASE, the denominator was the absolute BASE mean. For comparisons between two non-BASE scenarios, the denominator was the average absolute mean of the two scenarios:

$$\Delta_{rel} = \frac{\bar{x}_A - \bar{x}_B}{0.5(|\bar{x}_A| + |\bar{x}_B|)}$$

In addition, d_z was reported as a paired effect-constancy measure:

$$d_z = \frac{\bar{d}}{s_d}$$

Thus, d_z expresses the mean same-day difference relative to the variability of the same-day differences. Negative values indicate that scenario A is lower than scenario B, while positive values indicate the opposite. Larger absolute values indicate a more homogenous paired difference across days, but not necessarily a larger hydrological effect. This distinction is important because a physically small but highly consistent difference can have a large d_z , whereas Δ , and Δ_{rel} better describe the magnitude of the scenario shift. Therefore, interpretation was based jointly on $CI_{95}(\Delta)$, Δ_{rel} , d_z , the paired p-value, and *paired* n_{eff} .

1.4 Pipeline: GIS-Python-SWAT Workflow

A python pipeline was developed to ensure a reproducible workflow to assess the relative contribution of point- and non-point sources to nutrient loads into Cubillas reservoir (Walter, 2026). The pipeline consists of several thousand lines of Python with a focus on data provenance, which were developed with assistance from the LLM-based Microsoft Copilot tool to maximize cross-platform scalability, reproducibility, and adjustability. The pipeline scripts are published on *github.com* (Walter, 2026). The workflow consists of a series of steps including (in this order) GIS data loading, harmonization, scenario uncertainty bounding, generation of SWAT files, SWAT ensemble simulation, dashboard diagnostics of model response to different scenarios, and batch comparisons of sensitive statics and charts. Those steps can be grouped in two stages. In the first stage, a GIS is used to explore and analyse different data sources and to construct spatially continuous rasters covering the studied sub-basin. The second step is automatized and is largely based on Python scripts developed in this thesis. The GIS-generated rasters generated in stage 1 are processed to generate ensembles of input files, SWAT simulations conducted for each member of the ensemble of input files, and the simulated nutrient concentrations in the river from the ensemble of simulations visualized and compared with the existing water quality data.

Our starting point is the hydrological and erosion model developed for Cubillas watershed within the project, using ArcMap, ArcSWAT, and RSWAT. Input-files and output files are available from Fernández de Villarán et al. pers. comm (2025). SWAT was configured with the default/generic initialization procedures, and without any point-sources of nutrients. The model setup was recreated

locally to enable controlled scenario simulations and ensemble runs for uncertainty analysis. This configuration allowed automated model execution and systematic variation of uncertain inputs, enabling evaluation of their effects on simulated hydrological and water-quality outputs.

A customizable dashboard ([03_dashboard_RCH_analysis.ipynb](#)) was developed to compare SWAT .rch output ranges against measured data in a flexible manner. The tool overlays uncertainty envelopes from SWAT runs with the observations at the control stations in any sub-basin, enabling rapid inspection of temporal trends, assessment of basic assumptions, and visual and statistical quantification of uncertainty effects. By aligning the observed time series (derived from $\text{mg L}^{-1} \times \text{m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$) with the corresponding reach-level SWAT outputs, the dashboard facilitates visualizing whether observed values fall within simulated ranges and what systematic deviations occur. This interactive view supports focused interpretation and fast iteration while preserving the provenance of both model outputs and observations. Any water quality variable at any reach in SWAT can be compared against observations, as long as such are available. Another Notebook ([04_sensitivity_stats.ipynb](#)) allows to batch compare several statistical metrics between different scenarios and regimes against each other and check and visualize for significance of difference in a report ready way.

2 Results

2.1 Workflow for Automated Point-Source Definition in SWAT

To introduce point-sources in SWAT the user can either prescribe their magnitude and timing through the ArcSWAT interface, or, alternative, point-sources can be specified through user-generated load files (.dat) containing time series of flow rates and constituent concentrations (suspended sediments, N and P species, CBOD, dissolved oxygen, and chlorophyll-a) at daily, monthly or yearly resolution. (Arnold, Srinivasan, et al., 2012b). Independently of the approach used, a single point-source load can be specified for each subbasin, with these loads introduced into the river network at the upstream end of the reach associated with the respective subbasin. The fate and transport of constituents are then simulated and routed downstream through the river network. Here, the second approach was used, and according *.dat* loading files were generated via a script, allowing automated creation of multiple scenarios with varying loading levels. The workflow developed is here described, and the details of its implementation for Cubillas are given.

References to *.dat* input files must be manually added into the *.fig* watershed network configuration file (Figure 1). The *.fig* config file defines in which order contributions from HRUs - aggregated at sub-basin scale - and point sources accumulate downstream via river reaches. One point-source file must be defined for each subbasin/reach.

SWAT uses commands that declare sub-basin configuration and their routing/accumulation paths (e.g., SUBBASIN, ROUTE, ADD; see Figure 8). It also allows to define where SWAT reports aggregate outputs at intermediate reach outlets. All elements (subbasin, reach, point-source and intermediate aggregates) are encoded using an agnostic Hydrological Storage Number (HYD), which defines the topological connectivity of the system from upstream to downstream. Intermediate aggregates are HYDs that aggregate (ADD) the contributions of two other elements. Only once aggregated, the inputs of several subbasins and point sources can be routed through a reach (ROUTE). (Arnold, Srinivasan, et al., 2012a)

```

1  ▾ subbasin      1    1    1
2  |             |    |    |
3  ▾ subbasin      1    2    2
4  |             |    |    |
5  ...[ommiting 29 lines]...
6  recyear        8    901   1
7  pnt.source     rcyr_1.dat
8  recyear        8    902   2
9  pnt.source     rcyr_2.dat
10 ...[ommiting 29 lines]...
11 add            5    2002  1  901
12 ▾ route        2    18    1  2002
13 |             |    |    |
14 add            5    1008  4  904
15 add            5    19    1008 18
16 ▾ route        2    20    4    19
17 |             |    |    |
18 ...[ommiting 59 lines]...
19 ▾ saveconc     14    50    1    0
20 |             |    |    |
21 finish        0

```

Figure 8: A shortened version of a *.fig* file with point sources. The first number-column defines the command (Subbasin=1, Point-source=8, add=5, route=2. The second number-column sets the HYD number created by a command. The third and fourth number columns set the input HYD elements of the command. Colours indicate element types represented by the HYD. Subbasins (green), reaches (red), point sources (orange) and intermediate aggregates (blue).

A script was developed ([customize fig configs.ipynb](#)) that, given the original *.fig* file of a basin and a folder with one (dummy) *.dat* file per subbasin/point-source, constructs a correct *.fig* basin configuration with point sources accounted for (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). Another script (*point_dat.py*) is later used by the Montecarlo pipeline to dynamically populate the *.dat* point-source files with different values per realization.

To better grasp the routing logic, a network representation of the *.fig* declared HYD connectivity was developed. Figure 9 shows the visualization after introducing 17 point sources to the original Cubillas configuration, including subbasins (green), reaches (red), point sources (orange) and intermediate aggregates (blue).

Figure 9: Network (python) visualization of the Cubillas .fig config. Within the .fig all elements and intermediate aggregates (blue) are encoded via a Hydrological Storage Number (HYD), feeding into each other from top to bottom. For clarity HYD numbers representing certain elements get semantic labels in this graph. Original Subbasins (green) & Reaches (red) and programmatically inserted POINT SOURCES (orange).

2.2 Interpolated Soil Nutrient Concentrations

The interpolation exercise showed contrasting performance for Olsen-P (Fig. 10) and TKN (Fig 11). For TKN, leave-one-out cross-validation indicated moderate predictive skill and good overall calibration, with near-zero bias (-0.003%), RMSE of 0.382%, median absolute relative error of 47.0%, and 66.9% of predictions falling within a factor of two of the observations. For Olsen-P, predictive uncertainty was considerably larger: bias was -4.13 mg P2O5 per 100 g soil, RMSE was 28.67 mg/100 g, the median absolute relative error reached 64.6%, and only 43.5% of predictions were within a factor of two. Nevertheless, the 95% prediction interval coverage remained high for both nutrients, at 97.9% for TKN and 92.9% for Olsen-P, indicating that the kriging uncertainty estimates were broadly consistent with the observed prediction error (see Table 5).

Figure 10. Olsen-P interpolation, reported as P_2O_5 and clipped to the Cubillas catchment. Simple Kriging with trend in ArcGIS Pro was selected as the best method from leave-one-out cross-validation over the full UGRB plus a 30 km buffer evaluating 255 non-zero REDIAM topsoil observations (bias = -4.13, RMSE \approx 28.7, maximum absolute error \approx 136 mg P_2O_5 per 100 g soil, RMSSE = 1.07).

Figure 11. TKN interpolation clipped to the Cubillas catchment. Ordinary Kriging – Optimized in ArcGIS Pro was selected as the best method from leave-one-out cross-validation over the full UGRB plus a 30 km buffer considering 326 non-zero REDIAM topsoil observations (bias \approx -0.003, RMSE \approx 0.38, maximum absolute error \approx 4.8% of soil, RMSSE = 0.81).

Aggregated statistics computed for each spatial unit (i.e., the Upper Genil River Basin or the Cubillas catchment, rather than individual pixels or points) indicate that interpolation and aggregation substantially reduce local extreme values (see Table 6). The reduction in extremes occurs in two

stages. First, the transition from observed point measurements to the interpolation surface over the wider UGRB domain lowers the maximum values, from 5.94% to 1.77% for TKN and from 192.36 to 76.89 mg P2O5 per 100 g soil for Olsen-P. Second, within the Cubillas study area, aggregation of the Cubillas-clipped raster to HRU means lowers the maxima further, to about 0.34% for TKN and 26.12 mg P2O5 per 100 g soil for Olsen-P. The corresponding decrease in relative variability in the final HRU inputs therefore reflects both the change from point observations to a continuous interpolated surface and the subsequent change from raster cells to HRU-scale averages.

Table 5: Comparative leave-one-out cross-validation performance of the selected interpolation models for TKN and Olsen-P, calculated after excluding zero-valued observations.

Metric	TKN interpolation	Olsen-P interpolation
Non-zero samples	326	255
Bias	-0.003 % of Soil	-4.13 mg P2O5 / 100 g soil
RMSE	0.382 % of Soil	28.67 mg P2O5 / 100 g soil
Mean absolute relative error	95.1 %	2525.6 %
Median absolute relative error	47.0 %	64.6 %
P75 absolute relative error	99.0 %	203.1 %
Predictions within factor 2	66.9 %	43.5 %
95% interval coverage	97.9 %	92.9 %

Table 6: Comparative field structure of intermediate TKN and Olsen-P datasets constructed for soil-pool initialization, CV = coefficient of variation

Extent	Representation	TKN (% per SOIL)						Olsen-P (mg P2O5/100 g soil)					
		n	min	median	mean	max	CV	n	min	median	mean	max	CV
UGRB	Observed points	326	0.02	0.1	0.2	5.9	197%	255	0.01	17.5	28.6	192.4	109%
	Interpolation	≈68×10 ⁶	0.00	0.2	0.2	1.8	91%	≈68×10 ⁶	-1.09	21.1	22.2	76.9	59%
Cubillas	Interpolation	≈7×10 ⁶	0.00	0.1	0.1	0.5	98%	≈7×10 ⁶	0.00	3.7	6.3	26.1	117%
	HRU averages	878	0.10	0.2	0.2	0.3	26%	878	3.42	11.2	11.9	26.1	54%

2.3 Model Performance: River Flow Rates and Sediment Loads

Simulated monthly-averaged flow rates are shown as a function of time in Fig. 12, together with monthly inflow records into the Cubillas Reservoir provided by the Confederación Hidrográfica del Guadalquivir (CHG).

Overall, the model satisfactorily reproduces both the temporal variability and the magnitude of reservoir inflows, capturing seasonal patterns as well as most of the major hydrological events observed during the study period.

Model performance was evaluated by comparing simulated and observed daily inflows. Different calibration and validation period combinations were tested, and the most robust partition was obtained using 1981–2009 for calibration and 2010–2020 for validation. For the validation period, the model achieved a Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) of 0.51, a Kling–Gupta Efficiency (KGE) of 0.71, a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.54, and a Percent Bias (PBIAS) of 0.86%. These statistics indicate satisfactory model performance, with low bias and a good representation of the overall hydrological dynamics of the watershed.

Although some discrepancies remain during individual high-flow events, the model adequately reproduces the long-term water balance and the temporal evolution of reservoir inflows. Therefore, the model provides a reliable basis for evaluating sediment transport processes and their impacts on reservoir operation and storage conditions.

Given the absence of observed sediment transport measurements within the Cubillas watershed, sediment model evaluation was performed indirectly using estimates derived from reservoir bathymetric surveys. These surveys indicate an average sedimentation rate equivalent to approximately $3.7 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ at the watershed scale, corresponding to an annual sediment input of approximately $2.36 \times 10^5 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$.

The initial SWAT configuration produced sediment yields substantially lower than those inferred from the bathymetric analysis. Consequently, a dedicated sediment calibration was undertaken. This calibration focused on HRUs located on the steepest slopes, where erosion processes are expected to be most active. In addition, the USLE cover-management factor (C) and support-practice factor (P) associated with each land-use class were revised within the SWAT database in order to better represent local erosion conditions.

To increase sediment delivery through the river network, the channel sediment routing parameters were also adjusted. The sediment transport coefficient (SPCON) and exponent (SPEXP) were assigned values at the upper end of the physically reasonable calibration range, thereby increasing channel transport capacity and reducing intermediate sediment deposition. This calibration strategy was specifically designed to maximize sediment connectivity between hillslopes and the reservoir.

Following these modifications, the model produced an average sediment yield of $1.85 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, corresponding to an annual sediment production of approximately $1.18 \times 10^5 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$ for the 638.3 km^2 watershed. The calibrated model therefore reproduces approximately 50% of the sediment yield inferred from the bathymetric record.

An important aspect of the calibration procedure is that these sediment-related modifications did not deteriorate the hydrological performance previously achieved during flow calibration. The statistical

indicators used to evaluate streamflow simulations (NSE, KGE, R^2 and PBIAS) remained essentially unchanged after modifying erosion, transport and deposition parameters. This indicates that the improvements introduced in the sediment module were achieved without compromising the representation of watershed hydrology.

It should also be noted that a configuration intended to maximize sediment transport and minimize intermediate channel deposition was explored. Despite this, simulated sediment yields remained below those inferred from the bathymetric surveys. This suggests that the observed discrepancy cannot be attributed solely to excessive sediment deposition within the modelled river network.

Remaining differences between simulated and inferred sediment loads may reflect uncertainties not only in hillslope erosion processes, but also in the representation of channel geometry, hydraulic conditions and sediment transport during flood events. In SWAT, sediment routing strongly depends on the estimation of peak flow velocity and channel transport capacity. Consequently, uncertainties in channel dimensions, channel slope, hydraulic geometry relationships, or the simulation of extreme runoff events may significantly affect the amount of sediment ultimately delivered to the reservoir.

Considering the uncertainties associated with both modelling and bathymetric methods, the agreement achieved after calibration can be considered satisfactory. Although the model underestimates sediment production relative to the bathymetric estimates, both approaches yield sediment production estimates of the same order of magnitude. The results therefore support the suitability of the calibrated hydrological–sediment modelling framework for assessing long-term sedimentation processes and evaluating reservoir management scenarios in the Cubillas watershed.

The 40-year simulation period was subdivided into two subsets based on flow conditions: periods of low flow (baseflow conditions) and periods of high flow (storm-event conditions) (see Fig. 12). The rationale for this subdivision lies in the consistent evidence in the scientific literature that nutrient loads and concentrations in rivers reach their highest values during high-flow (storm) events (Kelly et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2022). This has been attributed to enhanced hydrological connectivity and the activation of rapid transport pathways during storm events, promoting nitrogen losses via leaching and phosphorus losses via erosion and sediment mobilization. Concentrations generally peak on the rising limb or near peak flow, with phosphorus showing an early, sharp peak due to erosion and sediment mobilization, and nitrogen exhibiting more variable timing depending on subsurface transport contributions (Bieroza & Heathwaite, 2015; Bowes et al., 2005).

Storm events (high-flow conditions) here were identified by periods of at least two consecutive days during which flow exceeds the 75th percentile of SWAT simulated flows ($Q_{75\text{pctile}} = \sim 167000 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$ for SOIL and $\sim 170000 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$ for WASTE and W+S) and had a two-day buffer added before and after these identified periods (lowest flow of a buffer day being $\sim 54000 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$). So, three days with flows above the 75th percentile were interpreted as a 7-day flow event. Of the 14245 simulated days $\sim 28\%$ were classified as high-flow periods. All other days ($\sim 72\%$) were treated as baseflow (low-flow) conditions. In general, available field data are biased and predominantly represent baseflow conditions. For example, almost 2/3 of the available water quality data for TN correspond to baseflow conditions, the remaining representing observations under high-flows (not necessarily peak-flows). Only one observation corresponded to a buffer day as per the definition above. Simulated and observed flow rates are plotted in Fig. 12. Coloured bands identify high- and base-flow periods. Note that, in general, SWAT tends to underestimate the observed flow rates (even

at monthly scales). Differences between observed and simulated flows are maximal during wet periods (see, for example, year 1997). Peak flows also tend to be underestimated by the model. The high-flow/baseflow split with the above criteria only changes marginally using the observed water flow (30% of the days are identified as high-flow).

Figure 12: High-flow days (pink background) and baseflow days (blue background) with monthly means of measured (dotted line) vs. swat simulated (continuous line) water flows. Time is given in natural years (i.e. starting in January).

2.4 Nutrient Transport Sensitivity: Shifts Relative to BASE

Simulated TP and TN concentrations and loadings at the test site, reach 13, were expected to increase compared with the default SWAT configuration when point sources were included, soil nutrient concentrations were initialized from soil pit sampling, or both effects were included. To assess the significance, magnitude and consistency of scenario-driven differences, paired daily contrasts among the WASTE, SOIL, and W+S simulations were calculated for average concentrations and loadings across all days, high-flow conditions, and baseflow conditions. The results are shown in Figs. 12 and 14 and summarized in Tables 6 and 7. In general, comparisons of mean shifts showed that nutrient concentrations under all scenarios differed significantly from BASE (one-sample t-test; $p < 0.001$ in all cases).

When averaging across all days, clear and consistent differences in loadings emerged among the scenarios (Fig 12, Table 7). For TP, WASTE loadings were significantly and impactfully lower than both SOIL and W+S, with relative paired differences of about -92%. SOIL and W+S were much closer to each other, differing by only about -6.6%, although this smaller contrast was significant across all regimes. TN, shows the same significance and impact patterns: WASTE was 87–89% lower than SOIL and W+S, whereas SOIL and W+S differed by about 12.5%.

Under high-flow conditions, WASTE remained much lower than the diffuse-source scenarios for both nutrients. The WASTE-vs-SOIL and WASTE-vs-W+S contrasts were all significant and reached about -98% for TP loadings and about -91% for TN loadings. In contrast, the SOIL–W+S differences were much smaller, while still significant: about -1.6% for TP and -9.9% for TN. This suggests that high-flow loading responses are dominated by the diffuse soil-related contribution, with only a small additional effect from adding point sources to the SOIL scenario.

During baseflow, the TP loading contrast between WASTE and SOIL largely disappeared, with a statistically unresolved relative difference of only -3.2%. However, W+S remained significantly higher than both WASTE and SOIL, with relative differences of about -51% and -49%, respectively. For TN, large WASTE-vs-diffuse contrasts persisted during baseflow, around -84% to -87%, while the SOIL–W+S contrast while significant remained smaller, about -14%. This demonstrates that for nitrogen, the contrast between pollution sources remains strong even during low flows, whereas for phosphorus, the differences fade away.

Between scenario concentration differences were all significant (Fig 13, Table 8) and broadly mirrored the loading contrasts, but their magnitude depended strongly on flow regime and nutrient. For TN, WASTE remained much lower than SOIL and W+S across all flow conditions, while SOIL–W+S differences were consistently smaller, around 8–10%. For TP, high-flow concentrations again showed strong WASTE-vs-diffuse contrasts, whereas baseflow concentrations showed a different pattern: WASTE exceeded SOIL, but W+S remained higher than both single-source scenarios. Overall, the tables support a dominant diffuse-source influence for TN in general and high-flow TP, while TP under baseflow shows a stronger combined-source response.

Daily median-of-envelope shift compared to BASE (total loads)

Figure 13: Absolute shift relative to the BASE scenario for TP and TN loads under WASTE, SOIL, and W+S, shown for all-day mean shift, all-day median shift, high-flow mean shift, and baseflow mean shift.

Daily median-of-envelope shift compared to BASE (concentrations)

Figure 14: Absolute concentration BIAS introduced under three load scenarios (WASTE, SOIL, and W+S) compared to the BASE scenario. Differentiating all day, high-flow and baseflow days

TABLE 7. Pairwise comparisons of mean load shifts across scenarios for TN and TP under all-flow, high-flow, and baseflow conditions. Reported statistics include the mean relative widths of each scenario, the 95% confidence interval of the paired absolute difference Δ , the paired relative difference Δ_{rel} , the paired effect-constancy measure d_z , the paired p-value, and the autocorrelation-adjusted paired effective sample size n_{eff} .

Flow	TP/ TN	Comparison	95% CI of Δ , paired (kg / day)	Δ_{rel} paired	d_z paired (effect constancy)	p paired	n_{eff} paire d
All days	TP	WASTE - SOIL	[-558, -208]	-92.2%	-0.10	<0.001	1957
		WASTE - W+S	[-585, -239]	-92.7%	-0.11	<0.001	1954
		SOIL - W+S	[-30.7, -27.8]	-6.6%	-0.77	<0.001	2542
	TN	WASTE - SOIL	[-1380, -1070]	-87.0%	-0.41	<0.001	1331
		WASTE - W+S	[-1590, -1260]	-88.6%	-0.46	<0.001	1341
		SOIL - W+S	[-206, -195]	-12.5%	-1.52	<0.001	2044
High flow	TP	WASTE - SOIL	[-2010, -772]	-97.7%	-0.19	<0.001	553
		WASTE - W+S	[-2020, -798]	-97.6%	-0.19	<0.001	555
		SOIL - W+S	[-28.2, -17.6]	-1.6%	-0.32	<0.001	695
	TN	WASTE - SOIL	[-2500, -1600]	-90.6%	-0.41	<0.001	474
		WASTE - W+S	[-2760, -1820]	-91.4%	-0.44	<0.001	475
		SOIL - W+S	[-268, -227]	-9.9%	-1.09	<0.001	474
Baseflow	TP	WASTE - SOIL	[-9.30, +7.22]	-3.2%	-0.01	0.805	1202
		WASTE - W+S	[-41.0, -24.4]	-51.0%	-0.22	<0.001	1210
		SOIL - W+S	[-31.9, -31.5]	-49.4%	-5.35	<0.001	3775
	TN	WASTE - SOIL	[-1300, -524]	-84.2%	-0.62	<0.001	58
		WASTE - W+S	[-1490, -697]	-86.5%	-0.73	<0.001	57
		SOIL - W+S	[-184, -181]	-14.4%	-3.14	<0.001	3791

TABLE 8. Pairwise comparisons of mean concentrations shifts across scenarios for TN and TP under all-flow, high-flow, and baseflow conditions. Reported statistics include the mean relative widths of each scenario, the 95% confidence interval of the paired absolute difference Δ , the paired relative difference Δ_{rel} , the paired effect-constancy measure d_z , the paired p -value, and the autocorrelation-adjusted paired effective sample size n_{eff} .

Flow	TP/ TN	Comparison	95% CI of Δ , paired (mg / L)	Δ_{rel} paired	d_z paired	p paired	n_{eff} paired
All days	TN	WASTE - SOIL	[-22.0, -4.56]	-86.2%	-0.43	0.004	50
		WASTE - W+S	[-23.1, -6.25]	-87.3%	-0.51	0.001	48
		SOIL - W+S	[-1.76, -1.04]	-8.3%	-0.43	<0.001	313
High-flow	TP	WASTE - SOIL	[-2.70, -1.55]	-94.1%	-0.43	<0.001	287
		WASTE - W+S	[-2.79, -1.67]	-94.1%	-0.46	<0.001	287
		SOIL - W+S	[-0.115, -0.0929]	-4.4%	-0.98	<0.001	365
	TN	WASTE - SOIL	[-7.68, -4.52]	-88.5%	-0.62	<0.001	153
		WASTE - W+S	[-8.45, -5.31]	-89.6%	-0.70	<0.001	151
		SOIL - W+S	[-0.805, -0.739]	-10.1%	-2.54	<0.001	328
Baseflow	TP	WASTE - SOIL	[+0.0724, +0.280]	+52.1%	+0.10	<0.001	1054
		WASTE - W+S	[-0.408, -0.239]	-38.8%	-0.22	<0.001	1127
		SOIL - W+S	[-0.566, -0.434]	-59.9%	-0.63	<0.001	566
	TN	WASTE - SOIL	[-27.2, -4.85]	-86.0%	-0.46	0.006	40
		WASTE - W+S	[-28.3, -6.98]	-87.0%	-0.54	0.002	39
		SOIL - W+S	[-2.13, -1.15]	-8.1%	-0.43	<0.001	230

2.5 Uncertainty in Simulated Nutrient Transport

Figure 15 presents the min–max envelope (shaded band) of annual average nutrient loads under the W+S scenario, derived from simulations using lower and upper bounds of all uncertain parameters, together with the mean/median time series (black line). Here, SOIL-input uncertainty is represented

by perturbing the mean soil nutrient concentrations using \pm the median of the absolute relative interpolation error. For Figs. 16 and 17, a more conservative assumption is used: the min–max bounds are computed with the same mean soil nutrient concentrations as in Fig. 15, but replacing the median with the 75th percentile of the absolute relative interpolation error for input perturbations, which widens the uncertainty envelopes. If the resulting lower bound factor is negative, it is treated as 0.

TOT_Nkg - Reach 13 (1A, mean) [Load kg/day]

Figure 15: W+S vs. BASE predictions for yearly averages of TN kg/day loads produced at reach 13. Diffuse soil inputs are perturbed using the absolute median of relative error of the input TKN interpolation. Point source inputs are perturbed using local population counts and literature wastewater composition ranges.

Only when the 75th percentile of the relative soil interpolation error is used to derive the min–max envelopes in the W+S scenario—the most conservative approach and thus least likely to underestimate uncertainty—do the BASE results fall within the uncertainty band (see Figs. 16 and 17).

TOT_Nkg - Reach 13 (1A, mean) [Load kg/day]

Figure 16: TN yearly averages of kg/day predictions; (W+S), using P75 of relative interpolation error for SOIL input perturbation.

TOT_Pkg - Reach 13 (1A, mean) [Load kg/day]

Figure 17: TP yearly averages of kg/day predictions; (W+S), using P75 of relative interpolation error for SOIL input perturbation.

In what follows, initial soil nutrient contents within each HRU, derived from interpolated rasters, are perturbed using multiplicative factors corresponding to the 75th percentile of the relative interpolation error, generating conservative upper- and lower-bound estimates of interpolation uncertainty for SOIL and W+S scenarios.

The mean values of R_t (i.e. mean relative width) computed over all simulation days, and separately for high-flow and baseflow periods, are presented in Fig. 18 for TP (above) and TN (below) across the three scenarios.

Relative envelope width - daily (max-min)/median

Figure 18: Relative min-max envelope widths of simulated TP (above) and TN loads (below) at the test reach.

The results are also summarized in Tables 8 (TN) and 9 (TP), where paired daily contrast statistics are provided for pairwise comparisons between scenarios.

For TN, SOIL perturbations consistently produced higher mean relative widths than WASTE across all flow conditions. The paired contrasts between SOIL and W+S were statistically resolved, but their relative magnitudes were very small during all flow regimes, approximately 0.7–1.0%. This suggests that soil-related processes are the dominant driver of TN uncertainty across flow conditions, while adding point-source inputs does not materially increase TN variability beyond the diffuse soil-driven contribution. (Table 9)

For TP, clearly significant paired differences were observed across the scenario comparisons. Across all-flow conditions, the highest mean relative widths occurred in the W+S scenario, followed by WASTE and SOIL. This indicates that the combined perturbation produced larger TP relative widths than either single-source perturbation alone. Under high-flow conditions, SOIL exceeded WASTE, while W+S was higher than SOIL. Under baseflow conditions, W+S again produced the highest values, followed by WASTE and SOIL. (Table 10)

Independently of flow condition, TN relative widths were much lower for WASTE than for SOIL and W+S, while SOIL and W+S remained very close in hydrological magnitude. For TP, differences in relative widths across scenarios were more pronounced, with W+S consistently highest and the ordering of SOIL and WASTE varying by flow condition. SOIL exceeded WASTE under high-flow conditions, whereas WASTE exceeded SOIL under baseflow and across all simulation days. Overall, TP showed a stronger response to combined source perturbations than TN, while TN uncertainty was mainly controlled by the SOIL perturbation.

Table 9. Pairwise comparisons of mean relative widths across scenarios for TN under all-flow, high-flow, and baseflow conditions. Reported statistics include the mean relative widths of each scenario, the 95% confidence interval of the paired absolute difference Δ , the paired relative difference Δ_{rel} , the paired effect-constancy measure d_z , the paired p -value, and the autocorrelation-adjusted paired effective sample size n_{eff} .

Flow condition	Comparison	Mean relative widths	CI95(Δ)	Δ_{rel} paired	d_z paired	p paired	n_{eff} paired	Interpretation
All-flow	WASTE vs SOIL	0.91 vs 1.91	[-1.05, -0.933]	-70.5%	-2.67	<0.001	148	SOIL > WASTE
All-flow	SOIL vs W+S	1.91 vs 1.89	[+0.0147, +0.0209]	+0.9%	+0.83	<0.001	190	SOIL slightly > W+S
High-flow	WASTE vs SOIL	0.65 vs 1.89	[-1.30, -1.19]	-98.0%	-3.67	<0.001	133	SOIL > WASTE
High-flow	SOIL vs W+S	1.89 vs 1.88	[+0.0117, +0.0163]	+0.7%	+0.91	<0.001	177	SOIL slightly > W+S
Baseflow	WASTE vs SOIL	1.01 vs 1.91	[-0.976, -0.819]	-61.4%	-2.65	<0.001	73	SOIL > WASTE
Baseflow	SOIL vs W+S	1.91 vs 1.89	[+0.0153, +0.0232]	+1.0%	+0.83	<0.001	137	SOIL slightly > W+S

Table 10. Pairwise comparisons of mean relative widths across scenarios for TP under all-flow, high-flow, and baseflow conditions. Reported statistics include the mean relative widths of each scenario, the 95% confidence interval of the paired absolute difference Δ , the paired relative difference Δ_{rel} , the paired effect-constancy measure d_z , the paired p-value, and the autocorrelation-adjusted paired effective sample size n_{eff} .

Flow condition	Comparison	Mean relative widths	CI95(Δ)	Δ_{rel} paired	d_z paired	p paired	n_{eff} paired	Interpretation
All-flow	WASTE vs SOIL	1.43 vs 1.24	[+0.0776, +0.313]	+14.6%	+0.21	0.0012	237	WASTE > SOIL
All-flow	W+S vs WASTE	1.72 vs 1.43	[+0.242, +0.332]	+18.2%	+0.62	<0.001	409	W+S > WASTE
All-flow	W+S vs SOIL	1.72 vs 1.24	[+0.399, +0.565]	+32.6%	+0.81	<0.001	201	W+S > SOIL
High-flow	WASTE vs SOIL	0.97 vs 1.56	[-0.717, -0.470]	-46.9%	-0.80	<0.001	143	SOIL > WASTE
High-flow	SOIL vs W+S	1.56 vs 1.67	[-0.152, -0.0680]	-6.8%	-0.43	<0.001	144	W+S > SOIL
Baseflow	WASTE vs SOIL	1.61 vs 1.11	[+0.394, +0.598]	+36.4%	+0.63	<0.001	233	WASTE > SOIL

2.6 Model Performance for Nutrient Concentration and Loads

Figure 19 presents an example of the visual exploration workflow, showing scenario envelopes and observations over the full simulation period for which TN measurements are available. Time series of TN concentrations simulated by SWAT for the BASE and W+S scenarios are plotted together with the sparse observations (dots) and the simulated flow rates. Shaded background regions (cyan and salmon) indicate baseflow and high-flow conditions, respectively. For the W+S scenario, the min–max uncertainty envelope is shown as a green shaded band, while the mean of the upper and lower bounds is represented by the black line.

Figure 20 presents a similar plot for TP, but over the shorter period from September 2000 to April 2001. Two TP samples were collected during this interval. In addition, sedimentation rates within the reach of subbasin 13 along the Cubillas River—immediately upstream of the reservoir (validation reach)—are also shown, calculated as the difference between sediment inflow and outflow loads. The largest discrepancy between observed and simulated TP concentrations among all 25 TP records in the dataset occurs in March 2001, during the recession phase during and shortly after the recession phase of a peak inflow event. In this case, simulated concentrations are nearly two orders of magnitude higher than the observations. This behaviour occurs consistently across all simulated scenarios.

TOT_Nkg - Reach 13 (1D, flow_weighted_mean) [Conc mg/L] vs. NITROGENO KJELDAHL; NITRATOS

Figure 19: Dashboard visualization of W+S and BASE scenarios' mean, and min-max predictions compared to all 18 available measurements of TN mg/L concentrations; Measurement symbols differ between those covered by the min-max uncertainty of the the W+S scenario and those not covered as well as by "event" (high-flow) and "non-event" (baseflow) conditions.

TOT_Pkg - Reach 13 (1D, mean) [Conc mg/L] vs. FOSFORO TOTAL

Figure 20: Dashboard visualization of S+W model min-max envelope compared to two measurements of the 25 available TP mg/L concentrations (diamonds); scenario. Contextualized by SWAT simulated water flow (blue) and measured waterflow (dotted blue) in m3/d as well as Sedimentation (tons/d).

Given the sparse and heterogeneous sampling, conventional goodness-of-fit metrics applied directly to the raw observations provide limited information. To better assess model–data agreement under these conditions, we compute (i) envelope coverage, defined as the proportion of observed values falling within the simulated uncertainty (min-max) envelope, and (ii) bias diagnostics, defined as the systematic difference between simulated and observed values and. Percent bias (PBIAS) was used as a descriptive relative bias diagnostic. It was calculated from the signed residual sum between simulated and observed values, normalized by the observed sum, and therefore indicates whether a simulation tends to overestimate or underestimate observations in relative terms. Mean bias was used as the corresponding absolute bias diagnostic. The implied observed mean shown in the figures is only an algebraic diagnostic derived from the relationship between mean bias and PBIAS for the same matched sample set.

Simulated vs. measured (concentrations)

Batch Folder Exports, Csv P75 Absolute Relative Error, All, Conc, Soil interpolation error: 75th percentile | all days, event definition: above 75th flow percentile, R13, nonnum half_MDL

Figure 23: all days; simulated vs measured concentration coverage and bias stats; TP observations = 25; TN = 18

The quality of model fit varied depending on the nutrient (TP or TN) and the scenario when considering the full dataset (Fig. 23). For TP, the envelope derived from simulations with perturbed point-source (WASTE) inputs captured 64% of observations, whereas the envelope based on perturbations of initial soil concentrations (SOIL) captured only 12%. Coverage increased only marginally in the combined W+S scenario (68%). For TN, unlike TP, WASTE performed worst in terms of coverage (11.1%), while SOIL and W+S both showed substantially higher coverage of 67%. Thus, the ability of the model to bracket TP observations was primarily driven by wastewater (WASTE) perturbations, whereas for TN it was mainly driven by soil (SOIL) perturbations.

Similar patterns in model performance across scenarios, as observed in the envelope coverage analysis, are also evident in the bias metrics. For TP, all scenarios overestimated concentrations on average, with mean bias increasing from +0.19 mg L⁻¹ in the WASTE scenario to +0.34 mg L⁻¹ in the SOIL scenario and +0.70 mg L⁻¹ in the W+S scenario; the corresponding PBIAS values were +62%, +111%, and +230%, respectively. For TN, WASTE overestimated concentrations only slightly, with a mean bias of +1.5 mg L⁻¹ and a PBIAS of +26%, whereas SOIL and W+S both vastly overestimated TN to a similar extent, with mean biases of +30 mg L⁻¹ and PBIAS values of +513% and +509%, respectively.

Simulated vs. measured (concentrations)

Batch Folder Exports, Csv P75 Absolute Relative Error, Non Events, Conc, Soil interpolation error: 75th percentile | non-event days, event definition: above 75th flow percentile, R13, nonnum_half_MDL

Figure 24: baseflow days; simulated vs measured concentration coverage and bias stats; TP observations = 18; TN = 12

When only considering baseflow conditions (Fig. 24), overall coverage improved and the contrasting behaviour between TP and TN became more evident. For TP, WASTE and W+S captured 68.% and 74% of observations, whereas SOIL captured only 5%. For TN, coverage increased from 15% under WASTE to 77% under SOIL and W+S. Bias for TP under baseflow conditions remained low, with WASTE showing a small positive mean bias (+0.13 mg L⁻¹; +35.9% PBIAS), SOIL a small negative bias (-0.08 mg L⁻¹; -22.5%), and W+S a larger positive bias (+0.35 mg L⁻¹; +99.8%). For TN, however, the differences in mean bias between scenarios were much stronger: WASTE overestimated considerably (+5 mg L⁻¹; +140%), whereas SOIL and W+S extremely overestimated concentrations (both +43 mg L⁻¹; +1137% and +1123%).

Simulated vs. measured (concentrations)

Batch Folder Exports, Csv P75 Absolute Relative Error, Events, Conc, Soil interpolation error: 75th percentile | event days, event definition: above 75th flow percentile, R13, nonnum_half_MDL

Figure 25: high-flow days; simulated vs measured concentration coverage and bias stats; TP observations = 7; TN observations = 6

Coverage worsens under high-flow conditions and the largest differences between TP model results and observations (error) can be observed while TN predictions become less biased. TP coverage ranged from 33% to 50%, with the WASTE and W+S envelopes each including half of the six observed events, while SOIL captured only one third. TP was overestimated in all scenarios, with mean biases of +0.4, +1.6, and +1.8 mg L⁻¹ for WASTE, SOIL, and W+S, respectively, corresponding to PBIAS values of +268%, +1150%, and +1250%. As for TN, coverage was 40% for SOIL and W+S while the WASTE scenario captured 0% of measured high-flow concentrations. All scenarios underestimated TN concentrations under high flow conditions (mean biases of -8, -5, and -4 mg L⁻¹ and PBIAS values ranging from -77% to -40%).

Overall, mean bias was more strongly controlled by flow regime than by scenario. Within each regime, differences between scenarios were most apparent between WASTE and SOIL scenarios, W+S inheriting the bias primarily from SOIL. Coverage was also affected by flow conditions. Under baseflow, TP coverage ranged from 5% to 74% and TN coverage ranged from 15% to 77%. Under high-flow conditions, TN coverage dropped to 0% in WASTE and 40% in SOIL and W+S, while TP coverage reached its base-flow maximum of 50% in WASTE and W+S scenarios. In summary, a major limitation of model performance appears to be its ability to represent storm conditions alongside the way uncertainty is introduced. Across all scenarios under high-flow conditions, TP was highly overestimated and TN consistently underestimated.

Table 11: TN comparison of baseflow (BF) and high-flow (HF) mean bias' of simulated-observed mg/L values on a certain day of measurement. Compare Fig. 24-25.

Scenario	Baseflow (mg L ⁻¹)	High-flow (mg L ⁻¹)	Δ (HF – BF)	Interpretation
WASTE	+5	-8	-13	Switch from BF overestimation to underestimation in HF
SOIL	+43	-5	-48	Switch from strong BF overestimation to underestimation in HF
W+S	+43	-4	-47	Switch from strong BF overestimation to underestimation in HF

Table 12: TP comparison of baseflow (BF) and high-flow (HF) mean bias' of simulated-observed mg/L values on a certain day of measurement. Compare Fig. 24-25.

Scenario	Baseflow (mg L ⁻¹)	High-flow (mg L ⁻¹)	Δ (HF – BF)	Interpretation
WASTE	+0.1	+0.4	+0.3	Stronger overestimation in HF
SOIL	-0.1	+1.6	+1.7	Switch from underestimation in BF to strong overestimation in HF
W+S	+0.4	+1.8	+1.4	Much stronger overestimation in HF

2.7 Flow-sorted Concentration/Load Curves

Flow-sorted concentration and loading curves were constructed as follows. For each simulation day, ensemble statistics (minimum, median, and maximum) of the target variable (either TP or TN concentrations or loads evaluated at reach 13) were computed across the available simulation runs and paired with the corresponding discharge for that day (which remains fixed across realizations). Days are ranked by the ensemble-mean simulated daily discharge (arithmetic mean of FLOW_OUT across all N Monte Carlo realisations for each calendar day) and assigned a flow-percentile position (0–100 %), such that the x-axis spans conditions from the driest (left) to the wettest (right). The simulated min-max envelopes are plotted against this flow-percentile axis, preserving the day-level pairing between water-quality variables and water discharge; observed values are placed at the flow percentile corresponding to their calendar day. Finally, a 60-day rolling average is applied to the central tendency to reduce synoptic-scale variability introduced by sorting more than 14,000 simulated loads by flow regime. The reader should note a key distinction between our flow-sorted curves and the traditional hydrological approach: while classical duration curves rank flows from highest to lowest, our x-axis utilizes an ascending rank percentile. Consequently, high-flow runoff events and their associated loads appear on the right side of the plot rather than the left, resulting in an upward-sloping baseline.

The flow-rated concentration curves for TN and TP under the W+S scenario are shown in Figures 26 and 28, respectively.

Consistent with our previous analysis (Fig. 23), the observed TN concentrations are reasonably well encapsulated by the model envelope under low-flow conditions, having a considerable positive bias though (see Fig. 26). While, during high-flow (storm) events, bias becomes smaller but relative coverage worsens. This indicates that the introduced uncertainties are realistic during dry periods but struggle to capture the detailed effects of storm events in TN concentrations, slightly underestimating higher pollution peaks.

TOT_Nkg – Concentration vs Flow Percentile

Figure 26: TN Flow sorted min-max prediction envelope and day-paired WFD measurements for all days. Measurement symbols are differentiated by whether they fall within the uncertainty envelope (shape) and whether they occurred on a baseflow or high-flow day (colour); rolling smoothing window for mean: 60 days.

In the case of TP (Fig. 28), the observed concentrations are also reasonably well reproduced by the model under low-flow conditions, remaining within the uncertainty range while lying slightly below the median prediction. Under high-flow conditions, though, the model tends to overpredict TP concentrations, which remain below or near the lower bound of the uncertainty range.

TOT_Pkg – Concentration vs Flow Percentile

Figure 27: TP Flow sorted min-max prediction envelope and day-paired WFD measurements for all days. Measurement symbols are differentiated by whether they fall within the uncertainty envelope (shape) and whether they occurred on a baseflow or high-flow day (colour); rolling smoothing window for mean: 60 days.

3 Discussion

3.1 Framework Objectives and Uncertainty Design

This study uses an approach that explicitly accounts for uncertainty in the available data, instead of relying on heavy calibration of the model. Rather than trying to fine-tune parameters to match observations too closely, the focus is on checking how well the model reproduces overall patterns and whether observations fall within predicted ranges. Different sources of pollution—such as municipal wastewater and diffuse inputs from soils—are tested separately to understand their individual influence on river conditions. The results are evaluated using simple visual tools, including range plots and flow-duration curves, to see how total nitrogen and phosphorus behave under both high-flow and low-flow conditions. This reproducibly implemented workflow helps ensure that the main conclusions remain reliable, even when data are limited or uncertain.

3.2 TN Dynamics and Source Attribution Across Flow Regimes

Total Nitrogen dynamics are overwhelmingly dominated by diffuse inputs (SOIL) across all metrics and flow conditions. Because the wastewater TN contribution accounts for only ~10% of the combined signal, the W+S scenario remains very close to the SOIL scenario, indicating that adding wastewater uncertainty changes TN results only modestly compared with the diffuse soil signal. While absolute TN loads peak during storm events, relative envelope widths and concentration shifts are significantly higher under baseflow conditions due to the dilution of point-source effluent during high discharge. Notably, the diffuse TN envelope width shows no significant regime effect, indicating that the Soil Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) releases soil-nitrogen proportionally across both wet and dry periods via continuous groundwater leaching, mineralization, and overland storm runoff.

3.3 Divergent Pathways of Point vs Non-point TP Across Flow Regimes

Unlike nitrogen, the dominant source of Total Phosphorus changes completely between baseflow and high-flow conditions. During storm events (high-flows), SOIL's non-point sources dominate the model response, exhibiting a 43-fold increase in load shift compared to baseflow (Fig. 13). This is likely the result of soil phosphorus being routed almost exclusively via surface runoff and its sediment transport. Conversely, during baseflow, SOILS' diffuse TP signal shifts the model by the same amount as WASTE, while W+S indicates an additive source response of W and S inputs.

3.4 Practical Implications for Catchment Monitoring

These contrasting nutrient behaviors expose a critical monitoring vulnerability in semi-arid catchments like the Cubillas. Because the diffuse TP signal is strictly "regime-gated" to storm events, the current quarterly low-flow grab-sampling strategy systematically misses the dominant non-point phosphorus pulses, leading to highly inaccurate annual load estimates that fail to separate point from non-point sources. Conversely, because diffuse TN maintains a persistent, slow-release component during low flows, dry-weather grab samples still carry genuine non-point source information,

demonstrating that monitoring frameworks must be fundamentally tailored to the unique transport pathways of each nutrient.

3.5 Structural Model Limitations vs. Input Data Uncertainty

Model validation reveals that observation coverage—the ability of the simulated min–max envelopes to bracket real-world data—varies depending on the specific nutrient considered and flow regime, alongside the modelling scenario. For Total Phosphorus (TP), coverage is driven almost entirely by the uncertainty in the magnitude of point-sources; the WASTE scenario alone captures 64% of all observations, whereas the diffuse SOIL scenario fails during dry weather (capturing just 5% of baseflow data) because its low-flow prediction envelope is structurally too narrow to bracket the measurements. Conversely, Total Nitrogen (TN) coverage follows the inverse pattern and is dominated by the uncertainty in the magnitude of the initial soil concentrations; the SOIL scenario captures 77% of baseflow observations, and incorporating wastewater uncertainty in the combined W+S scenario yields no coverage boost, confirming that continuous effluent from soils is the dominant TN signal during low-flow periods. However, envelope coverage should not be interpreted as absence of bias: under baseflow, SOIL and W+S bracketed many TN observations but still showed large positive concentration biases, meaning that the uncertainty range can contain observations while the central model tendency has a bad fit.

During high-flow events, the model is less able to reproduce observed conditions, and these discrepancies can likely not only be explained solely by uncertainty in the input data. The model underestimates nitrogen transport during storm events and strongly overestimates TP: TN coverage drops to 0% when considering only wastewater input ranges and captures only 40% for scenarios incorporating diffuse soil inputs, while for TP, coverage ranged from 33% under SOIL to 50% under WASTE and W+S. The weaker performance during storms suggests that a major problem lies in how the model represents high-flow conditions, and not only in the specific scenario assumptions used. Overall, the results suggest that the model does not correctly represent how nutrients are transported during storms. It greatly overestimates phosphorus concentrations during high-flow events, while at the same time underestimating nitrogen concentrations.

3.6 Strengths of Analysis Approach

Our approach explicitly tracks uncertainty using simulation 'envelopes' and tests different pollution sources side by side (SOIL, WASTE, and W+S). This approach makes it easy to see both how much the model's predictions spread out (sensitivity) and how much they shift compared to the baseline (BASE) and comparing scenario contrasts statistically. By adding flow-specific qualitative tools like Load Duration Curves, we can clearly separate how the model performs during storm events versus dry weather—a feature that is crucial when working with sparse, irregular water quality measurements. Furthermore, this framework and its software pipeline are built to be reproducible and expandable. If any new input data can be mapped across the catchment with a justifiable range of uncertainty, it can be easily plugged in, re-run, and compared using the exact same steps.

Regarding the soil data, the interpolation methods used to set up the initial soil conditions successfully calculated realistic spatial averages, but they have known limitations when dealing with extreme values. Statistical checks showed that the interpolation was generally unbiased and well-calibrated. However, scatterplots revealed that it systematically underestimated areas with very high

nutrient concentrations. This happens because soil chemistry is heavily skewed, meaning a few localized 'hotspots' dominate the landscape. While Kriging provided reliable average values for each sub-basin (HRU), it naturally smoothed out these extreme hotspots. This smoothing effect was an expected limitation that we explicitly factored into the model uncertainty analysis. The choice of uncertainty bound also matters: only the conservative P75 interpolation-error perturbation was wide enough for the W+S annual-load envelope to include the BASE simulation, so source-attribution conclusions depend partly on adopting this broader soil-input uncertainty range.

3.7 Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting our results and point to specific avenues for future research. First, available riverine TP and TN concentration data are sparse and biased, as they are predominantly collected under baseflow conditions. Moreover, the current simulation period does not include the more recent, higher-quality monitoring data available after 2020. Given the limited data availability, the treatment of below-detection-limit values—whether included or excluded—may influence conclusions regarding model performance. To address this, future work should establish a high-frequency monitoring campaign upstream of the Cubillas Reservoir, complementing official Demarcación Hidrográfica del Guadalquivir records and improving the representation of variability under critical flow conditions. Since high-flow events contribute disproportionately to overall loads, monitoring campaigns should prioritize event-based sampling designs.

The representation of peak flows and sediment-associated phosphorus processes will likely require targeted calibration to adequately capture the dynamic behaviour of TP during inflow events. In particular, the current model appears to over-amplify or mistime sediment-associated TP transport during storm conditions, suggesting that important transport and mobilization processes are insufficiently represented. This may include limitations in the simulation of erosion, sediment resuspension, particulate phosphorus transport, and the timing and magnitude of runoff generation during high-flow events. Since phosphorus transport in Mediterranean catchments is often strongly associated with sediment mobilization during short, intense rainfall events, improving the representation of these processes is likely essential for reproducing observed TP dynamics. Future work should therefore focus on refining flow routing and sediment transport parameters, while also incorporating higher-frequency monitoring data during storm events to better constrain calibration under transient hydrological

The current min–max uncertainty bands remain conservative, as they are based on simplified assumptions regarding error propagation. In the present framework, uncertainties from different sources are combined using fixed minimum and maximum ranges, implicitly assuming that errors accumulate linearly and independently. However, environmental processes and model responses are often highly non-linear, meaning that uncertainties may interact, amplify, or compensate for one another in more complex ways. As a result, the current approach may overestimate uncertainty in some situations while underrepresenting it in others. A more robust alternative would be the application of Monte Carlo uncertainty propagation, in which model inputs and parameters are repeatedly sampled from probability distributions to generate ensembles of possible outcomes. Such an approach would allow a more realistic characterization of uncertainty ranges, improve the representation of parameter interactions, and provide probabilistic estimates of nutrient loads and concentrations under different hydrological conditions.

For direct comparisons, measured concentrations were converted to loads using SWAT-predicted flows. However, river flows in the present implementation of SWAT in Cubillas are not corrected for abstractions or diversions out of the basin. Naturalized inflow rates have been reconstructed from available information; however, the dataset remains incomplete and highly uncertain. For example, there is no information on water abstractions to irrigation channels within the river, nor on pumping rates from alluvial riparian aquifers that may be draining water from the river. Also, groundwater discharge into the river at Deifontes Spring is highly uncertain and is estimated from sparse gauging measurements by the Confederación Hidrográfica del Guadalquivir and from continuous diversion flow records from water utilities supplying spring water. Those adjustments have likely a minor effect on concentrations during peak flows, but they could be important during baseflow conditions. Their effect (particularly diversions into the river) on nutrient concentrations could be strong, especially under baseflow conditions. For example, interbasin transfer inflows through Colomera channel (largely concentrated in summer, under base flow conditions) is sourced in the hypolimnion of Colomera reservoir. Hypolimnetic nutrient concentrations (dissolved phosphorus or ammonia, mainly) could be well above the expected concentration of those nutrients under baseflow conditions in Cubillas reservoir.

Point-source loads have been estimated from urban census data, assuming fixed but uncertain per-capita loadings, thereby implicitly assuming that urban wastewater discharges represent the dominant point source. However, for the reconstruction of historical reservoir loadings, additional sources should be considered, particularly olive oil mill wastewater (OMWW), which prior to the 1980s was frequently discharged directly into river systems. Olive oil mill wastewater (OMWW) is widely recognized as one of the most polluting effluents generated by agro-industrial activities in Mediterranean regions. Its environmental impact is primarily associated with its extremely high organic load, reflected in very high chemical oxygen demand (COD) and biological oxygen demand (BOD), as well as its high concentration of phenolic compounds, which are toxic, persistent, and difficult to biodegrade. Reported COD values can reach up to 170 g L^{-1} and BOD up to 110 g L^{-1} , indicating a strong oxygen-depleting potential when discharged into aquatic systems. In addition, phenolic compounds may occur at concentrations of several g L^{-1} and are considered the main drivers of OMWW toxicity to aquatic organisms due to their antimicrobial and phytotoxic properties. When released into rivers without treatment, OMWW can rapidly induce oxygen depletion, ecological stress, and biodiversity loss, particularly in low-flow conditions. Toxicity has been observed across multiple trophic levels, including algae, crustaceans, and fish, and is largely attributed to low-molecular-weight phenols such as hydroxytyrosol and catechol. These compounds can inhibit microbial activity, disrupt aquatic food webs, and persist in sediments, prolonging environmental impacts beyond the initial discharge event. Consequently, OMWW is consistently classified among the most hazardous liquid wastes generated by the olive oil sector in the Mediterranean basin.

Olive mill wastewater (OMWW) represents a significant pollution risk in aquatic environments not only because of its high organic and phenolic load (Afonso et al., 2025), but also due to its nutrient content, particularly nitrogen and phosphorus compounds. Total nitrogen is typically present in organic forms derived from proteins and amino compounds, while phosphorus is associated with both organic and mineral fractions. Olive mill wastewater (OMWW) is characterized by substantially higher nutrient concentrations than urban wastewater on a per-volume basis, despite its seasonal and episodic discharge pattern. Typical total nitrogen (TN) concentrations in OMWW range from approximately 0.5 to 3 g L^{-1} , while total phosphorus (TP) ranges from about 0.05 to 0.5 g L^{-1} .

L⁻¹ (Dermeche et al., 2013). In contrast, raw municipal wastewater generally exhibits TN concentrations of approximately 20–85 mg L⁻¹ and TP concentrations of 4–15 mg L⁻¹ (Metcalf, 2000). This indicates that OMWW may contain nutrient concentrations one to two orders of magnitude higher than urban wastewater, particularly for nitrogen. However, unlike municipal discharges, which are continuous throughout the year, OMWW is typically generated during the olive oil production season and was discharged (untreated) in short, high-intensity pulses, often under low-flow hydrological conditions. This combination of high nutrient concentrations and low dilution capacity can lead to disproportionate short-term nutrient loading to receiving waters, increasing the likelihood of nutrient accumulation in sediments and downstream reservoirs, where they can contribute to long-term internal loading (Paraskeva & Diamadopoulos, 2006). Furthermore, the high organic and phenolic content of OMWW can alter biogeochemical cycling, inhibiting microbial processes such as nitrification and thus modifying nitrogen transformation pathways in the receiving water body. As a result, even if nutrients are not the dominant pollutant fraction in OMWW, their release can still play an important role in driving eutrophication risk and ecological degradation in impacted river systems.

4 Conclusions

This thesis developed a reproducible GIS-Python-SWAT workflow to assess nitrogen and phosphorus transport in the Cubillas catchment under sparse monitoring conditions. Instead of relying on intensive water-quality calibration, the study used scenario-based uncertainty envelopes to compare point-source wastewater inputs (WASTE), diffuse soil-derived inputs (SOIL), and their combination (W+S).

The results show that source attribution is strongly nutrient- and flow-regime dependent. Total nitrogen was consistently dominated by diffuse soil inputs, which exceeded wastewater effects by roughly one order of magnitude across flow conditions. This indicates that simulated TN transport is mainly controlled by persistent diffuse pathways such as leaching, mineralization, groundwater contributions, and runoff.

Total phosphorus showed a clear source reversal. During storms, diffuse soil inputs significantly dominated TP transport, producing about a 40-fold larger load shift than the wastewater scenario. During dry weather, the diffuse TP signal weakened strongly, making wastewater comparable to or larger than soil inputs among single-source scenarios. Thus, TP export is highly event-skewed and closely tied to runoff, erosion, and sediment transport.

Daily SWAT simulations revealed behaviour that quarterly grab samples cannot resolve. In particular, annual non-point TP loads may be controlled by a small number of storm days, meaning that predominantly dry-weather monitoring is poorly suited to estimate annual phosphorus loading or separate point and diffuse sources in semi-arid catchments.

Model-data comparison showed useful but limited capability. Without water-quality calibration, W+S bracketed 74% of baseflow TP observations and 77% of baseflow TN observations, but coverage did not always imply low bias. The weakest performance occurred during high-flow events, where TN coverage fell to about 40% and TP to 50%, the later being strongly overestimated, pointing to limitations in peak-flow representation, sediment-associated phosphorus transport, event timing, and routing.

The wastewater implementation was internally consistent: WASTE-only loads were of the same order as independent population-based untreated-wastewater estimates, within about a factor of 1.3-1.7. This supports the plausibility of the point-source inputs.

Overall, the thesis shows that an uncertainty-explicit SWAT workflow can support source attribution even with sparse observations. Nitrogen and phosphorus require different monitoring and management strategies: TN has a persistent diffuse signature, whereas TP is storm-gated and sediment-linked. Future work should prioritize event-based monitoring, better peak-flow and sediment calibration, explicit treatment of diversions and abstractions, and full Monte Carlo uncertainty propagation beyond the current min-max approach.

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Appendices

A Sediment calibration parameters – 219

Parameters and ranges used by the working group for calibrating the sedimentary simulation for cubillas:

Parameter	Change	Min	Max	Best result
GW_DELAY.gw	replace	10	50	25.154
CN2.mgt	relative	-0.1	0.3	-0.032
SOL_K.sol	relative	-1	60	18.443
ALPHA_BF.gw	replace	0.1	0.9	0.548
ESCO.hru	replace	0.1	0.9	0.478
SURLAG.hru	replace	0.1	0.9	0.16
CH_K2.rte	relative	0.35	5	3.054
SURLAG.bsn	replace	5	10	8.825
SOL_AWC.sol	relative	-0.5	2	-0.045
REVAPMN.gw	replace	100	3000	673.773
GWQMN.gw	replace	100	3000	1808.743
RCHRG_DP.gw	replace	0.01	0.9	0.279
SOL_ZMX.sol	relative	-0.36	-0.28	-0.306
SOL_Z.sol	relative	0.5	2	1.931
SHALLST.gw	replace	150	2800	2616.059
LAT_TTIME.hru	replace	10	150	88.47
GW_REVAP.gw	replace	0.0001	0.2	0.014
SLSOIL.hru	relative	-0.2	0	-0.164
SLSUBBSN.hru	relative	0.1	2.5	1.567

B Land use lookup table: area covered within cubillas

SIOSE			SWAT		
Description	Code	(ha)	percent (%)	Code	Description
Casco urbano	111	101.25	0.16	URHD	Urban High density
Ensanche urbano	112	75.81	0.12	URML	Urban medium density

Urbano discontinuo	113	125.50	0.20	URLD	Urban low density
Zona verde urbana	114	1269.63	1.99	PAST	Pasture / grass
Instalación agrícola y/o ganadera	121	72.56	0.11	AGRC	General agriculture
Extracción minera	123	96.19	0.15	SWRN	Barren / rock
Zona industrial	130	56.75	0.09	UIDU	Urban industrial
Servicio dotacional	140	24.81	0.04	UINS	Urban institutional
Asentamiento agrícola / huerta	150	7.56	0.01	AGRL	General crop / mixed
Red viaria o ferroviaria	161	420.88	0.66	UTRN	Urban transportation
Infraestructura de residuos	172	8.44	0.01	UNIS	Urban institutional
Cultivo herbáceo	210	12841.94	20.12	SWHT	Crop land (general / row / grains)
Frutal no cítrico	232	115.06	0.18	ORCD	Orchards / vineyard / fruit trees
Olivar	234	24765.31	38.80	OLIV	Olive
Otros cultivos leñosos	235	659.81	1.03	ORCD	Orchards / vineyard / fruit trees
Combinación de cultivos	250	699.31	1.10	AGRL	General crop / mixed
Cultivos y vegetación natural	260	5039.69	7.90	RNGB	shrub
Bosque de frondosas	311	2960.31	4.64	OAK	Oak
Bosque de coníferas	312	2948.75	4.62	PINE	Forest evergreen pine
Matorral	330	10291.94	16.12	RNGB	Range / shrubland
Temp. desarbolado (incendio o tala)	353	1043.63	1.63	BARR	Barren / rock
Curso de agua	511	208.19	0.33	WATR	Water bodies
TOTAL		63833.31			

C Soil type lookup table: soil characteristics

Nomb re	Ave_DE P	Ave_B ULK_D ENSI	Ave_A WC_E U23_B	Ave_ CO	Ave_KS _MED	Ave_CLAY _EU23_	Ave_SILT _EU23_	Ave_SAN D_EU23_	Ave_C oarse	Ave_K _Usle
AGRO	111.778	1.292	0.112	0.833	5.174	30.211	41.638	28.151	22.17 0	0.288
AGR13	90.302	1.301	0.109	1.303	18.222	29.640	43.253	27.107	17.72 4	0.247
AGR14	88.571	1.342	0.099	1.019	19.085	25.426	46.390	28.184	16.88 4	0.262
AGR19	101.403	1.283	0.103	1.507	17.021	24.173	40.972	34.855	25.55 9	0.243
AGR2	117.801	1.327	0.097	0.818	18.208	27.473	42.700	29.827	13.17 2	0.306
AGR42	92.851	1.292	0.100	1.310	18.412	27.036	44.274	28.690	15.46 8	0.262
AGR44	89.434	1.287	0.108	1.328	17.781	28.900	42.847	28.253	20.68 2	0.265
AGR58	106.076	1.242	0.103	1.180	18.597	28.171	39.694	32.136	16.72 1	0.263

Column	Meaning in English	Unit
Ave_DEP	Average soil depth	cm
Ave_BULK_DENSI	Average soil bulk density	g/cm ³
Ave_AWC_EU23_B	Average available soil water capacity	mm/mm
Ave_CO	Average soil organic carbon	%
Ave_KS_MED	Average saturated hydraulic conductivity	mm/h
Ave_CLAY_EU23_	Clay content	%
Ave_SILT_EU23_	Silt content	%
Ave_SAND_EU23_	Sand content	%
Ave_Coarse	Average coarse fragments / coarse elements	%

Ave_K_Usle	USLE soil erodibility K factor	—
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D Validation data used

TABLE B: Validation data used: Rows: 43 dates (station 30304, study period 1981-01-01 to 2020-01-01, valid = non-negative numeric or LC). LC values were replaced with half of the lowest value reported in the whole dataset.

Date	Total Phosphorus (mg P/l)	Kjeldahl Nitrogen (mg N/l)	Nitrate (mg NO3/l)
1994-12-01		1.1	2.8
1995-02-01		1.9	1.5
1995-04-01		1	5.5
1995-11-01		1.7	7.3
1996-02-01			77.9
1996-05-01			51.9
1996-11-01			35.5
1997-03-06		1.6	50.7
1997-06-20		1.9	29.3
1997-10-28		1.1	23.3
1997-12-10		0.1 (LC)	45.2
1998-03-03		0.1 (LC)	48.2
1998-06-10		0.1 (LC)	38.9
1998-09-09	0.005 (LC)	0.1 (LC)	0.7
1998-12-03	0.52	0.1 (LC)	26.2
1999-03-16	0.66	0.1 (LC)	15.2
1999-06-01	0.23	0.6	5.2
1999-11-09	0.54	3.2	18.5
1999-12-01	0.59	0.1 (LC)	

2000-03-14	0.44	0.1 (LC)	
2000-06-06	0.17	0.1 (LC)	
2000-09-06	0.13	0.1 (LC)	0.05 (LC)
2000-12-20		0.1 (LC)	23.6
2001-03-08	0.06	1.3	48.4
2008-11-20	0.278		12.6
2009-01-21			12.33
2009-04-23	0.15		28.83
2009-09-15	1.32		16.39
2009-11-11	0.311		40.98
2014-09-01	0.07		17.049
2015-02-12	0.11		17.5
2015-06-09	0.87		17.3
2015-11-17	0.11		12.7
2016-02-11	0.17		12.1
2016-06-14	0.21		8
2016-11-15	0.09		11
2017-02-23	0.07		14
2017-06-27			6.4
2017-11-14	0.16		8
2018-02-13	0.12		8
2018-06-11	0.19		26
2019-06-26			8
2019-10-02			8

E Software and Computational Tools

SWAT 2012 (Soil and Water Assessment Tool) & RSWAT

Watershed simulation was conducted with **SWAT**, with initial watershed setup and calibration carried out via **RSWAT**.

Neitsch, S. L., Arnold, J. G., Kiniry, J. R., & Williams, J. R. (2011). *Soil and Water Assessment Tool theoretical documentation, version 2009*. USDA Agricultural Research Service.

Nguyen, V. T., Dietrich, J., Dang, T. D., Tran, D. A., Doan, B. V., Sarrazin, F. J., Abbaspour, K., & Srinivasan, R. (2022). An interactive graphical interface tool for parameter calibration, sensitivity analysis, uncertainty analysis, and visualization for the Soil and Water Assessment Tool. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 156, 105497.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2022.105497>

ArcMap + ArcSWAT

Winchell, M., Srinivasan, R., Di Luzio, M., & Arnold, J. G. (2013). ArcSWAT interface for SWAT2012: User's guide. *Texas A&M AgriLife Research and USDA Agricultural Research Service*.

ArcGIS

For exploration and interpolation

Python

A reproducible Python pipeline automated data transformations, file generation for SWAT, scenario assembly, and post-processing of outputs (including uncertainty-envelope summaries and regime-based diagnostics). All scripts were version-controlled and reviewed for consistency with the Methods.

Editorial Aids (language support)

Computer-aided editing tools were employed for clarity and consistency, namely Microsoft Word editor suggestions, DeepL, and LLM-assisted drafting aids. These tools were used solely for language support; all data analysis, interpretation, and citations were conducted and checked by the author.

Codex code assistance

Targeted **Codex**-based coding assistance was used for boilerplate generation and refactoring within the Python workflow

F Dashboard interface

Number of initializations: 2 - run 155

Variable:

Compare:

Method:

Units via:

Measured conversion: mg/L → kg/day using SWAT avg FLOW_OUT × 86400 = m³/day. Formula: kg/day = mg/L × m³/day × 0.001.

Aggregation: period sums in kg/day (measured converted daily then summed).

Simulation: series are in kg/day (no conversion).

Reach:

Freq:

Bin:

Auto-scale Y on zoom

Names in tooltip

Show range slider

Measured overlay

Show measured

Show water flow (m³/d)

Show SWAT avg flow (m³/d)

Show erosion (SED_IN - SED_OUT)

Events via: Min days:

Threshold:

View:

Buffer (days)

Events: days where flow >= threshold and lasting >= Min days. Use the view toggle to switch between event and non-event periods.

Non-numeric:

Negatives:

Flag deviations

Factor:

Map 1

Map 2

Map 3

Chem:

Stations:

Extra overlays

Show: BASE

Settings changed

TOT_Nkg - Reach 13 (1W, sum) [Load kg/day]

TOT_Nkg - Reach 13 (1W, sum) [Load kg/day]

TOT_Pkg - Reach 13 (1D, mean) [Load kg/day]

TOT_Pkg - Reach 13 (1W, mean) [Load kg/day]

Flow strat summary: regimes: event, non-event | total band on | mode: Min/Max envelope | layout: overlay | events=1624, non-events=3917 | meas pts=9

Simulation Load Duration Curve

Flow-stratified (event vs non-event)

Stats (view)

n = 9
 data usage = 0.2% of available days
 sim coverage = 100.0% (5535/5535 days)
 measured coverage = 100.0% (9/9 days)
Same-day
 r = -0.059
 R2 = 0.003
 MAE = 0.249
 RMSE = 0.274
 Bias(obs-pred) = -0.0655
 PBIAS% = -17.7
 NSE = -0.660
 KGE = -0.116

Diagnostics: TOT_Pkg (Reach 13)

KGE = -0.116
 MedAE = 0.236
 coverage50 = 33.3%
 coverage90 = 55.6%
 coverage100 = 77.8%
 NSE_rel = -0.66
 d = 0.384
 d_rel = 0.384
 RSR = 1.29

Distribution Summary

Observed (paired):
 mean = 0.37
 median = 0.44
 p05 = 0.082
 p25 = 0.17
 p50 = 0.44
 p75 = 0.54
 p95 = 0.632
 sd = 0.213
 var = 0.0454
 n = 9
 Predicted (paired):
 mean = 0.436
 median = 0.451
 p05 = 0.219
 p25 = 0.308

p50 = 0.451
 p75 = 0.522
 p95 = 0.632
 sd = 0.148
 var = 0.0219
 n = 9
 Predicted (full series):
 mean = 0.975
 median = 0.413
 p05 = 0.168
 p25 = 0.29
 p50 = 0.413
 p75 = 0.794
 p95 = 3.44
 sd = 2.18
 var = 4.74

Global lag

best lag = 2 d (by NSE)
 r = -0.034
 R2 = 0.001
 MAE = 0.204
 RMSE = 0.247
 NSE = -0.346

Local window K=1

RMSE = 0.261
 MAE = 0.228
 Bias(obs-pred) = -0.0585
 NSE = -0.497
 median_lag_days = -1
 IQR_lag_days = 2

Residuals (obs - pred): mean=-0.0655, sd=0.266, skew=0.273

Residual vs Predicted (median)

Local matching lags (K=1)

Reproduce diagnostics

```
from python_pipeline_scripts.stats import build_fit_diagnostics
# assuming you have q_df (fan quantiles) and measured_series from the dashboard context
figs = build_fit_diagnostics(q_df, measured_series, window=(pd.Timestamp('1986-01-01'), pd.Timestamp('2001-02-25')), template='plotly_white',
title="Diagnostics: TOT_Pkg (Reach 13)", lag_hist_k=1, compare_mode=('conc' if is_conc_mode else 'load'))
```